
Teaching Performance Through the Lens of Leisure Engagement and Sustainable Well-being: A Mediation Analysis

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ABSTRACT: The study explores the relationship between teachers' leisure engagement, their sustainable well-being, and teaching performance. Using a quantitative-correlational design with mediation analysis, a total of 136 teacher respondents from various schools were surveyed to assess their levels of leisure engagement, categorized by both type and degree, as well as their sustainable well-being across five key dimensions. Additionally, teachers' teaching performance was also evaluated through self-evaluations, peer evaluations, and student evaluations. A total of 369 students from various schools participated to assess their teachers' teaching performance across the seven domains aligned with PPST.

The result revealed that teachers were generally engaged in leisure activities, with the highest levels observed in passive and social forms. Sustainable well-being was rated to a great extent. Teaching performance was found to be outstanding across all domains, based on self-evaluations, peer evaluations, and student evaluations. Statistical analyses indicated significant relationships between leisure engagement and both sustainable well-being and teaching performance. Furthermore, sustainable well-being was found to mediate the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance significantly.

These findings highlight the essential role of well-being and leisure in enhancing professional performance, suggesting that policies and programs promoting teacher wellness and balanced lifestyle are crucial for sustainable educational success.

KEYWORDS: Leisure Engagement, Sustainable Well-being, Teaching Performance, Mediation Analysis

INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a dynamic, multifaceted profession that involves more than just classroom instruction; teachers have to find a balance between their personal and professional lives. In addition, teachers have to uphold academic standards, manage a variety of student needs, and fulfill administrative expectations, all of which can lead to stress and emotional exhaustion (Schaufeli & Bakker, 2006). Maintaining one's well-being becomes more important as these demands increase. Leisure activities offer opportunities for relaxation, rejuvenation, and personal fulfillment, making them a promising strategy to enhance teachers' overall well-being and effectiveness. Given these difficulties, leisure activities have drawn interest as a significant means of promoting teachers' long-term well-being, which will ultimately lead to better classroom instruction (Iwasaki, 2007).

In recent years, there has been growing interest in understanding how personal well-being and life outside the classroom contribute to professional effectiveness. This study, "*Teaching Performance Through the Lens of Leisure Engagement and Sustainable Well-being: A Mediation Analysis*," examined the complex relationship between teachers' leisure engagement, their sustainable well-being, and how these factors impact teaching performance.

To support mental health and overall life satisfaction, leisure engagement—defined as participation in activities undertaken for enjoyment, relaxation, and personal fulfillment during free time—is essential (Iwasaki, 2007; Kuykendall et al., 2015). Recreational activities helped teachers avoid stress, lower their risk of burnout, and develop emotional resilience—qualities that are crucial for sustaining good teaching performance (Sonnetag et al., 2007). According to Iwasaki (2007), this study divided leisure activities into five categories: active, passive, social, cognitive, and creative.

According to Deci et al. (2000), sustainable well-being refers to an individual's capacity to maintain a steady and satisfying state of mental, emotional, and physical health over an extended period. Teachers must prioritize their long-term health because they are frequently subjected to stressful situations and much work. Sustainable well-being, as defined by Dodge et al. (2012), refers to a psychological balance and life satisfaction that persists over time and across various contexts. The five dimensions of well-being—physical, emotional, social, workplace, and societal well-being—are interconnected; it is not a static state but rather a balance between them.

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Given the extended exposure to work-related stress, maintaining well-being is particularly important for teachers. According to Collie, Shapka, and Perry (2012), teachers who consistently feel well are more likely to exhibit higher levels of job satisfaction, professional commitment, and classroom effectiveness.

A key mediating factor in the relationship between leisure activities and teaching effectiveness is sustainable well-being. For teachers to succeed both personally and professionally, they must maintain sustainable well-being, which ensures that they can fulfill their job responsibilities without compromising their long-term health and happiness. Physical, emotional, and social health must also be considered in a multifaceted strategy to attain long-term well-being. Furthermore, workplace support is essential for promoting teachers' long-term well-being. Examples of this support include offering mental health resources, encouraging collaborative environments, and assigning manageable workloads (Collie et al., 2012). Teachers who prioritize their health can continue to be effective, stay motivated, and make a significant contribution to their students' success.

On the other hand, teaching performance refers to a teacher's ability to effectively guide students, manage classrooms, and create an encouraging learning environment. Pedagogical skills and professional competence are not the only factors that affect teaching performance. Effectiveness in the classroom is significantly influenced by teachers' personal well-being, encompassing aspects such as life satisfaction, mental health, and physical health. Unhappy, burned-out, or dissatisfied teachers are less likely to perform well in class, which can be detrimental to both the teacher and the students (Friedman, 2000). On the other hand, teachers who are resilient, driven, and satisfied tend to employ more effective teaching techniques, which in turn improve student learning. This study employs a mediation analysis to investigate whether leisure engagement influences teaching performance through the mechanism of sustainable well-being. By examining this connection, the study advances our understanding of how wellness practices and individual life experiences can be leveraged to enhance learning outcomes.

By highlighting the need to support teachers' holistic development beyond the realm of traditional professional training, the findings aim to inform both individual practice and institutional policy.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study intended to determine the relationship between leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance with a particular focus on how sustainable well-being mediated the effect of leisure engagement on teaching performance of 136 selected secondary school teachers and 369 selected students from Mauban South District namely: Dr. Maria D. Pastrana National High School, Cagsiay I National High School, and Cagbalete Island National High School.

The study sought to give answers to the following questions:

1. What is the level of leisure engagement among teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 Types of leisure engagement;
 - 1.1.1 Active;
 - 1.1.2 Passive;
 - 1.1.3 Social;
 - 1.1.4 Cognitive; and
 - 1.1.5 Creative?
 - 1.2 Degree of leisure engagement
 - 1.2.1 Frequency of leisure engagement;
 - 1.2.2 Intensity of leisure engagement; and
 - 1.2.3 Quality of leisure engagement?
2. What is the level of sustainable well-being among teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 Emotional well-being;
 - 2.2 Physical well-being;
 - 2.3 Social well-being;
 - 2.4 Workplace well-being; and
 - 2.5 Societal well-being?
3. What is the level of teaching performance among teachers as per self-evaluation, peer-evaluation, and students' evaluation in terms of:
 - 3.1 Content knowledge and pedagogy;
 - 3.2 Learning environment;
 - 3.3 Diversity of learners;
 - 3.4 Curriculum and planning;
 - 3.5 Assessment and reporting;
 - 3.6 Community linkages and professional engagement; and

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3.7 Personal growth and professional development?

4. Is there a significant relationship between leisure engagement and sustainable well-being?
5. Is there a significant relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance?
6. Is there a significant relationship between sustainable well-being and teaching performance?
7. Does sustainable well-being mediate the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed a quantitative-correlational research design to investigate the relationships between teachers' teaching performance, sustainable well-being, and leisure engagement.

Specifically, the study aimed to determine the mediating role of sustainable well-being in the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance.

Additionally, it seeks to determine the strength and direction of the relationship among the key variables – leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance – and to examine whether sustainable well-being serves as a mediating variable in the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance.

The study population is primarily composed of selected secondary school teachers and high school students from Mauban South District, including those from Dr. Maria D. Pastrana National High School, Cagsiy I National High School, and Cagbalete Island National High School. A random sampling technique was employed to ensure the inclusion of teachers across different educational levels, ages, and years of experience, as well as with students at various grade levels and ages.

The sample size was determined using Slovin's Formula, which helps ensure that the selected sample size is representative of the entire population.

The respondents were the selected 136 public school secondary teachers. Students were also part of the study, where students' evaluation is necessary to measure the teacher's teaching performance. The respondents are 369 selected high school students from Mauban South District, including those from Dr. Maria D. Pastrana National High School, Cagsiy I National High School, and Cagbalete Island National High School.

A total of 153 teachers are employed at Dr. Maria D. Pastrana National High School, from which a sample of 100 teachers was selected. Cagbalete Island National High School, with 21 teachers, contributed 14 teacher-respondents, while Cagsiy I National High School, which employs 33 teachers, had 22 participants in the sample. This distribution reflects a proportional sampling technique, ensuring that each school's representation aligns with its teacher population size. Distribution of student respondents across the same schools: Dr. Maria D. Pastrana National High School, with a student population of 3,857, provided the most significant sample of 304 students. Cagbalete Island National High School and Cagsiy I National High School, with 370 and 455 students respectively, had 29 and 36 respondents. The sample selection across all schools followed a proportional random sampling method to maintain the representativeness of the overall student population.

The selection strategy ensured both teachers' and students' perspectives were adequately represented, offering a balanced and comprehensive view of teaching performance in relation to leisure engagement and sustainable well-being.

This study utilized a structured survey questionnaire as the primary research instrument. The questionnaire consisted of four sections:

Part I. Respondents' Profile. This section pertains to the respondent's profile, which includes their name, school, age, gender, marital status, educational attainment, teaching position, and length of teaching experience.

Part II. Survey Questionnaire on Leisure Engagement. This corresponds with the teacher-respondents' level of engagement in both types and degree of leisure.

Part III. Survey Questionnaire on Sustainable Well-being. This corresponds with the teacher-respondents' level of sustainable well-being in different dimensions.

Part IV. Survey Questionnaire on Teaching Performance. This corresponds with the self-evaluation, student evaluation, and peer evaluation of teachers' teaching performance.

Standardized instruments were used in the survey, with each parameter comprising five questions. A validated self-made questionnaire was used. It is a researcher-designed survey instrument that has undergone a validation process to ensure reliability, accuracy, and relevance in measuring the intended variables.

To ensure the validity, a validated Likert scale-based questions for measuring leisure engagement with the scale of (5) Always; (4) Often; (3) Sometimes; (2) Rarely; (1) Never was used for the types of leisure engagement such as: active, passive, social, cognitive and creative. Degrees of leisure engagement will also be measured in terms of frequency, intensity, and quality. In measuring the frequency of leisure engagement, the scale is (5) Always; (4) Often; (3) Sometimes; (2) Rarely; (1) Never. Measuring the intensity of leisure engagement, the scale of (5) Extremely Intense; (4) Highly Intense; (3) Moderately Intense; (2) Slightly Intense; (1) Not At All Intense. While the Quality was measured with the scale of (5) Very Good, (4) Good, (3) Fair, (2) Poor, (1) Very Poor. Different dimensions of well-being will assess sustainable well-being, these include: emotional well-being,

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physical well-being, social well-being, workplace well-being, and societal well-being. This will be measured through the scale of (5) Strongly Agree; (4) Agree; (3) Neutral; (2) Disagree; (1) Strongly Disagree. For teaching performance, the 7 domains of the Philippines Professional Standard for teachers will be utilized to measure the teacher's teaching performance through self-evaluation, peer evaluation, and student evaluation. This will be measured through a rating scale of (5) Outstanding, (4) Very Satisfactory, (3) Satisfactory, (2) Unsatisfactory, (1) Needs Improvement.

The researcher adapted various theories and frameworks to develop the necessary parameters used in the survey questionnaire. After putting together, the various principles, frameworks, and parameters, the questionnaire was developed. To ensure the reliability and validity of the research instrument, a systematic validation process was conducted. A panel of six experts in the fields of education (public school district supervisor, school head, head teacher, master teacher, teacher III, English and Filipino Major) evaluated the questionnaire to assess its clarity, relevance, and appropriateness in measuring leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance.

The experts provided feedback and recommendations on item wording, structure, and alignment with the study objectives. Necessary revisions were made based on expert suggestions to enhance the content validity of the instrument.

A pilot test was conducted with a sample of 30 teachers and 30 students who were not part of the actual study to check the reliability of the instrument. The internal consistency of each section (Leisure Engagement, Sustainable Well-Being, and Teaching Performance) was assessed using Cronbach's Alpha coefficient.

Overall, the Cronbach's alpha results demonstrate that the instruments used in this study are reliable and internally consistent for measuring the constructs of leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance. The values mostly fall within the "acceptable" to "excellent" range, indicating that the items within each subscale reliably measure the intended constructs.

This study employed a structured procedure to examine the relationship between leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance. Initially, an extensive review of the literature was conducted to develop a conceptual framework and construct a validated survey questionnaire that measures leisure engagement (in terms of types and degree), sustainable well-being (encompassing physical, emotional, social, societal, and workplace aspects), and teaching performance (in relation to PPST domains). The questionnaire underwent expert validation for content relevance and pilot testing to ensure reliability, with necessary revisions made based on the feedback received.

Cronbach's Alpha was computed to assess the internal consistency and reliability of the research instrument, ensuring that survey items effectively measured their intended constructs. All statistical tests were conducted at a 0.09 level of significance, with data processing carried out using statistical software such as SPSS or AMOS to enhance accuracy. These statistical treatments provided empirical support for understanding the role of leisure engagement in fostering well-being and improving teaching performance, ultimately guiding policy recommendations for teacher well-being programs and professional development initiatives.

The target population consisted of teachers and students from various secondary school levels, and the sample size was determined using Slovin's formula. A random sampling technique was employed to ensure representation across school categories. Ethical considerations, including informed consent and confidentiality, were prioritized before distributing the survey online using Google Forms. After data collection, responses were reviewed, encoded, and analysed using descriptive statistics (mean, standard deviation) to determine the levels of leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance. Pearson's correlation analysis was applied to examine relationships between these variables, while mediation analysis determined the direct and indirect effect of sustainable well-being on teaching performance through leisure engagement.

The final results were synthesized and interpreted using statistical models, tables, and graphical representations to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationships among the study variables.

These findings contributed to recommendations on teacher well-being programs, work-life balance policies, and professional development initiatives, emphasizing the role of leisure engagement in enhancing overall teaching performance.

To analyse the collected data, this study employed various statistical methods to ensure the accurate and meaningful interpretation of the results. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to summarize the levels of leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance among teachers.

Pearson's correlation analysis was applied to determine the strength and direction of relationships between leisure engagement, sustainable well-being, and teaching performance. Establishing whether a significant association exists among these variables.

To further explore the mediating effect of sustainable well-being, using the Process Macro of Hayes Mediation analysis is a statistical technique that allows for an in-depth examination of whether sustainable well-being acts as a bridge between leisure engagement and teaching performance. The PROCESS macro, developed by Andrew F. Hayes (2022), is a widely used tool for conducting mediation, moderation, and conditional process analyses in SPSS or SAS.

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RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table 1: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types in terms of Active

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher ...</i>			
1. I enjoy participating in group activities such as dance, martial arts, or team sports (e.g. basketball, volleyball etc.)	3.71	1.18	Engaged
2. I participate in individual activities such as jogging, walking, swimming etc.	3.58	0.98	Engaged
3. I make time for fitness-related activities, such as going to the gym, working out, practicing yoga, or taking aerobics classes.	2.99	1.19	Moderately Engaged
4. I participate in outdoor activities such as hiking, cycling, mountain climbing etc.	2.78	1.26	Moderately Engaged
5. I take part in community-based active leisure like fun runs, sports festivals, or fitness classes.	3.59	1.02	Engaged
Overall	3.33	1.13	Moderately Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged, 3.50-4.49 Engaged, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged, 1.50- 2.49 Less Engaged, 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 1 shows that the highest level of engagement was observed in group activities, such as dance, martial arts, and team sports like basketball and volleyball ($m = 3.71$; $SD = 1.18$), with a verbal interpretation of "engaged." This suggests that teachers are more likely to engage in cooperative and social physical activities. Group-based leisure offers a sense of community, stress reduction, and peer support, which in turn motivates teachers. This was supported by studies such as Eime et al. (2013), which emphasize how playing team or group sports improves social ties and psychological well-being, providing support for this.

Likewise, individual activities such as jogging, walking, and swimming ($m = 3.58$, $sd = 0.98$) and community-based active leisure activities like fun runs, sports festivals, or fitness classes ($m = 3.59$, $sd = 1.02$) also showed high levels of engagement, as indicated by verbal interpretation of "engaged." These findings suggest that teachers often choose affordable, easily accessible physical activities that can be done in groups or individually. These kinds of activities are appealing because they are convenient and flexible, which is especially crucial for professionals with little free time.

However, lower levels of engagement were recorded in structured fitness-related activities, such as gym workouts, yoga, and aerobics ($m = 2.99$; $sd = 1.19$), as well as outdoor recreation, including hiking, mountain climbing, and cycling ($m = 2.78$; $sd = 1.26$), both with verbal interpretations of "Moderately Engaged." These activities frequently call for more preparation, time, money, and occasionally specialized facilities or equipment, all of which not all teachers may have easy access to. Working adults, including teachers, frequently participate in structured fitness activities and outdoor recreation at lower rates due to obstacles such as time constraints, cost, and facility accessibility. Individuals with rigorous work schedules are less likely to participate in structured physical activities, particularly those that require more preparation and resources (Brown & Payne, 2009). According to Caldwell (2005), professionals frequently under-participate in active leisure due to scheduling conflicts and occupational stress, despite the known health benefits.

Based on the data gathered, the overall mean score ($m = 3.33$; $sd = 1.13$) with a verbal interpretation of "Moderately Engaged" suggested that teachers participated in active leisure activities to a moderate extent. This suggested that although they did participate in physical activities, they did not do so regularly or consistently enough to be regarded as highly engaged.

The result was in line with the realities that many teachers, especially those in the public education system, currently face. Teachers in our district frequently face a heavy workload of administrative responsibilities and required trainings and seminars. Their time and energy for regular physical activities are often restricted by these obligations, particularly those that require a significant investment of time or resources, such as yoga classes, gym sessions, or outdoor excursions. Socioeconomic constraints might also be involved. Access to fitness center is not available to all teachers. Their limited funds might keep them from joining gyms or taking trips for outdoor recreation. The absence of systematic support also diminishes their opportunities for organized active leisure.

The variations between the specific indicators provided important information about the habits, problems, and preferences of teachers regarding active leisure. Promoting organized fitness and outdoor activities may therefore improve teachers' general well-being and performance, even though they show a moderate level of active leisure participation.

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Table 2: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types in terms of Passiv

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I watch television shows, movies, or streaming content for relaxation.	4.41	0.79	Engaged
2. I engage in reading books, magazines, or articles for leisure.	3.89	0.84	Engaged
3. I enjoy listening to music, podcasts, or audiobooks for relaxation.	4.34	0.80	Engaged
4. I browse social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, or Twitter, during my free time.	4.53	0.70	Highly Engaged
5. I spend my leisure time resting or napping.	4.11	0.85	Engaged
Overall	4.26	0.80	Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged; 3.50-4.49 Engaged; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged; 1.50-2.49 Less Engaged; 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 2 shows that the most frequently engaged passive activity among teachers was browsing social media platforms, such as Facebook, Instagram, and Twitter ($m = 4.53$; $sd = 0.70$), with a verbal interpretation of "Highly Engaged." The result may be explained by the quick accessibility and instant satisfaction offered by social media platforms. Teachers can interact with people on social media, watch entertaining content, and temporarily escape the stress of their jobs. Passive leisure, according to Iwasaki (2007), offers psychological separation from work-related stress, which is crucial for emotional healing and overall well-being.

Another highly rated activity is watching television shows, movies, or streaming content ($m = 4.41$; $SD = 0.79$) with verbal interpretation of 'Engaged', which provides teachers with a means for mental relaxation. These activities facilitate cognitive detachment from work demands and emotional catharsis. Reinecke and Eden (2017) provided support for this, noting that leisure media consumption serves as a coping mechanism for stress at work.

Listening to music, podcasts, or audiobooks also ranked high ($m = 4.34$, $SD = 0.80$) with verbal interpretation of 'engaged'. This form of passive leisure activity promotes mood improvement, emotional control, and cognitive stimulation. According to Schäfer et al. (2020), music listening, in particular, promotes psychological well-being by elevating mood and reducing anxiety.

Resting and napping received a mean of 4.11 ($SD = 0.85$) with a verbal interpretation of "Engaged," indicating that teachers recognized the importance of sleep-in preserving well-being and productivity. Rest and sleep are essential for cognitive recovery, particularly for individuals in mentally demanding occupations. The advantages of rest in enhancing focus, memory, and general performance were highlighted by Lo et al. (2016).

Lastly, reading books, magazines, or articles received a mean of 3.89 ($SD = 0.84$) with a verbal interpretation of "engaged." Reading for pleasure creates a contemplative and peaceful experience, offering mental stimulation. It also promotes intellectual fulfillment and personal development. Particularly in intellectually demanding occupations, such as teaching, research has repeatedly demonstrated the importance of sleep and rest for cognitive recovery, emotional control, and sustaining overall productivity. Due to extended periods of cognitive engagement, lesson planning, and classroom management, teachers frequently experience mental exhaustion. To recuperate and maintain performance, many people place a high value on rest and quick naps.

Lo et al. (2016) claim that getting enough sleep and napping can enhance working memory, attention, and emotional stability—all of which are essential for effective instruction. Likewise, Faraut et al. (2015) found that even brief naps (20–30 minutes) greatly enhance alertness and performance, particularly in individuals with sleep deficiencies.

The overall findings on the level of leisure engagement in terms of passive activities reveal that teachers are generally engaged in this type of leisure, with an overall mean of 4.26 and a standard deviation of 0.80. According to the findings, teachers actively participate in a variety of passive leisure activities, especially those that are accessible, low-effort, and emotionally fulfilling. These patterns of leisure engagement reflect the reality of many public-school teachers, particularly in Mauban South District, who are faced with numerous teaching and administrative responsibilities, many teachers tend to gravitate toward passive forms of leisure that are more convenient, less physically demanding, and easily accessible at home or through mobile devices.

These pursuits served as effective coping strategies for managing the pressures and stressors associated with teaching. This supports the findings of Chen and Fan (2022), who found that leisure activities improve teacher well-being and reduce the risk of burnout, particularly when they are regular and align with individual preferences.

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Table 3: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types in terms of Social

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I spend time with friends or family for fun and relaxation.	4.45	0.74	Engaged
2. I enjoy attending cultural or entertainment-based social activities (e.g., concerts, theater, festivals, and performances, religious gatherings)	3.75	1.06	Engaged
3. I engage in group activities such as team sports, board games or club meetings.	3.37	1.20	Moderately Engaged
4. I join environmental initiatives (e.g., clean-up drives, tree planting, feeding programs etc.)	3.71	1.02	Engaged
5. I attend workshops, seminars, or public lectures.	3.87	0.93	Engaged
Overall	3.83	0.99	Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged; 3.50-4.49 Engaged; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged; 1.50-2.49 Less Engaged; 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 3 shows that among the indicators, spending time with friends or family had the highest mean score ($m = 4.45$; $sd = 0.74$), with a verbal interpretation of "Engaged," indicating that teachers highly value this aspect of their relationships. Strong social ties are essential for happiness and emotional resilience, according to research by Diener and Seligman (2002). Engagement in cultural and entertainment-based events, such as concerts, festivals, and religious gatherings, was also rated highly ($m = 3.75$; $sd = 1.06$), with verbal interpretation indicating 'engaged'. According to Deng et al. (2020), these kinds of activities promote community and life satisfaction.

Participation in workshops, seminars, or public lectures ($m = 3.87$, $sd = 0.93$), with a verbal interpretation of "Engaged," indicates educators' dedication to intellectual and professional socialization, which can be used for both learning and recreation, according to Kolb (1984) and Illeris (2018).

Meanwhile, teachers also engage in environmental and civic initiatives such as clean-up drives, tree planting, feeding programs ($m=3.71$; $sd=1.02$) with verbal interpretation of Engaged, demonstrated their desire to make a significant contribution to society, which is in line with Wilson's (2020) research showing that civic engagement increased a person's sense of purpose.

The only indicator that fell under the Moderately Engaged category was participation in group activities, such as sports or clubs ($m=3.37$; $sd=1.20$), which suggested that time constraints or personal preferences might influence their engagement. This is supported by Zarrett et al. (2020), who discovered that although group activities strengthen social ties, teachers' hectic schedules frequently prevent regular participation.

The overall result of teachers' leisure engagement in terms of social activities revealed an overall mean of 3.83 and a standard deviation of 0.99, indicating that teachers are generally engaged in this type of leisure.

The results show that teachers in the Mauban South District engage in selective but balanced social interaction. These teachers still value social interaction, despite the demanding nature of their work, especially in more approachable or professionally relevant settings, such as family time or educational seminars. However, the district's lack of time, energy, or venues for group leisure activities, such as sports or club meetings, may be a contributing factor to the lower participation in these activities. Regular participation in group-based leisure activities may also be hindered by scheduling conflicts, transportation issues, or geographic dispersion of schools, especially in more rural or coastal barangays, such as those served by Cagbalete Island National High School and Cagsiyai I National High School.

Table 4: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types in terms of Cognitive

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I engage in problem-solving activities such as puzzles, crosswords, or Sudoku.	3.79	1.00	Engaged
2. I participate in activities that require critical thinking, such as debates or discussions.	3.41	1.11	Moderately Engaged
3. I spend time playing strategy-based games like chess or card games.	3.24	1.15	Moderately Engaged
4. I like learning new skills or hobbies that challenge my mind.	4.01	0.98	Engaged
5. I watch educational videos, documentaries, or attend lectures to expand my knowledge.	4.34	0.85	Engaged
Overall	3.76	1.02	Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged; 3.50-4.49 Engaged; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged; 1.50-2.49 Less Engaged; 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 4 shows that the highest mean score was observed in watching educational videos, documentaries, or attending lectures ($m = 4.34$; $sd = 0.85$), with a verbal interpretation of "Engaged." This suggested that a large number of educators relied on multimedia materials as their primary source of cognitive stimulation. This aligns with Illeris (2018), who highlighted how adaptable and captivating platforms, such as educational media, greatly benefit modern adults by fostering lifelong learning and cognitive development.

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The second-highest mean score was from the statement, “learning new skills or hobbies that challenge my mind” ($m = 4.01$; $sd = 0.98$), with a verbal interpretation of “Engaged,” which again suggested a strong inclination among teachers towards activities that push their cognitive limits. Mezirow (2000) provided support for this, stating that learning transformations often begin when people willingly seek out challenging new experiences that alter their perspectives and abilities.

Engagement in problem-solving activities, such as puzzles, crosswords, and Sudoku ($m = 3.79$; $sd = 1.00$), also received an Engaged rating. These types of activities were known to promote memory retention, focus, and problem-solving abilities, which are crucial for educators. According to Green and Bavelier (2012), cognitive games enhance decision-making and attention control abilities, which are applicable to instructional strategies and classroom management.

However, two indicators were rated as Moderately Engaged: participating in activities that required critical thinking, such as debate or discussion ($m = 3.41$, $SD = 1.11$), and playing strategy-based games like chess or card games ($m = 3.24$, $SD = 1.15$). These findings demonstrate that although some educators take pleasure in intellectually challenging group or competitive games, others may not regularly engage due to time constraints, disinterest, or accessibility issues. Zarett et al. (2020) noted that although cognitive leisure activities can significantly enhance cognitive function, regular engagement often depends on a person's time constraints and perception of the activities' value.

The overall result on cognitive leisure engagement showed that teachers were actively engaged in activities that stimulate the mind, with an overall mean of 3.76 and a standard deviation of 1.02, which falls under the category of “Engaged.”

The data presents the intellectual commitment and adaptive mindset of teachers in the Mauban South District; despite the many challenges they faced in public education. Teachers in this area consistently engage in cognitively enriching activities, aligning with the expectation of the teaching profession that demands lifelong learning, critical thinking, and adaptability. The high engagement in watching educational materials and learning new skills underscores their initiative to stay informed and relevant, particularly as they navigate the evolving demands of the K-12 curriculum and digital education. However, moderate engagement in more interactive cognitive leisure activities, such as debates, strategy games, and structured problem-solving, may indicate limited access to cognitive leisure platforms, a lack of peer engagement opportunities, or time constraints due to heavy workloads and administrative duties. This is particularly true in geographically dispersed schools, such as those on Cagbalete Island or Cagsiay, where isolation and limited resources may limit access to collaborative intellectual activities.

Table 5: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types in terms of Creative

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I enjoy writing poetry, stories, or other forms of creative writing.	3.31	1.09	Moderately Engaged
2. I play a musical instrument or compose music in my free time.	2.64	1.31	Moderately Engaged
3. I participate in the performing arts, including acting, dancing, and singing.	3.16	1.24	Moderately Engaged
4. I engage in drawing, painting, or other visual arts as a form of leisure.	2.94	1.28	Moderately Engaged
5. I engage in creative cooking or baking as a way to express myself.	3.35	1.33	Moderately Engaged
Overall	3.08	1.25	Moderately Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged; 3.50-4.49 Engaged; 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged; 1.50-2.49 Less Engaged; 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 5 shows that engaging in creative cooking and baking had the highest mean among all the indicators ($m=3.35$; $sd=1.33$), with a verbal interpretation of Moderately Engaged level implying that teachers turn to culinary creativity as an accessible and fulfilling leisure activity. Creative cooking as a leisure activity was found to be substantially associated with improved mental health, a greater sense of personal control, and greater life satisfaction in a study by Becker et al. (2022). This supported the idea that even non-traditional forms of creativity, such as baking or DIY crafts, can yield positive psychological outcomes for teachers. Participating in performing arts, such as acting, dancing, or singing, had a result of ($m=3.16$; $sd=1.24$) with a verbal interpretation of Moderately Engaged. This implies that even though not everyone participates in performing arts activities regularly, a sizable section of the populace nevertheless does so occasionally or somewhat regularly. Its moderate prevalence may be explained by the fact that participation in the performing arts is frequently linked to emotional expression, social connection, and personal enjoyment (Cuypers et al., 2012). Engaging in drawing, painting, or other visual arts as a form of leisure had a result of ($m=2.94$; $sd=1.28$) with a verbal interpretation of Moderately Engaged. The result demonstrated that while visual arts are a popular activity, they are not given much priority. Lack of materials or time constraints may be to blame for this. But according to Stuckey and Nobel (2021), creating visual art can help people become more mindful and reduce stress, particularly when professionals in emotionally taxing fields use it as a reflective tool. Playing musical instrument or compose music during free time with a mean score of ($m=2.64$; $sd=1.31$) still falls under Moderately Engaged but reflects a lower level of involvement compared to the other indicators. This may be due to the skill-specific nature of musical performance and the need for practice and equipment. According to a study by Van den Bosch et al. (2020), accessibility and previous training have a major impact on participation levels, even though creating music has therapeutic and cognitive benefits.

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Table 5 revealed the level of leisure engagement of teachers in terms of creative activities had an overall mean of 3.08 and a standard deviation of 1.25, the results suggested that teachers are Moderately Engaged in creative types of leisure. According to Clift et al. (2021), encouraging creativity can improve teacher well-being, encourage innovation in teaching strategies, and lessen burnout. They also emphasized that creative engagement can increase professional satisfaction and act as a stress buffer.

The results show that teachers in the Mauban South District have a moderate propensity for creative leisure, which could be impacted by a number of contextual factors. Regardless of the outcome, educators continue to find ways to express their creativity in ways that are more accessible and adaptable to their everyday routines, like writing or cooking projects. These outlets likely serve as stress relievers or personal coping strategies, helping them stay balanced in the face of teaching demands.

Table 6: Summary Table on Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Types

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Active	3.33	1.13	Moderately Engaged
Passive	4.26	0.80	Engaged
Social	3.83	0.99	Engaged
Cognitive	3.76	1.02	Engaged
Creative	3.08	1.25	Moderately Engaged
Overall	3.65	1.04	Engaged

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Highly Engaged, 3.50-4.49 Engaged, 2.50-3.49 Moderately Engaged, 1.50- 2.49 Less Engaged, 1.00-1.49 Not Engaged

Table 6 highlights the summary of the overall level of leisure engagement among teachers across five distinct leisure types: active, passive, social, cognitive, and creative. With an overall mean score of 3.65 and a standard deviation of 1.04, the data revealed that teachers are generally engaged in leisure activities. Among the five types, passive leisure recorded the highest mean ($m = 4.26$; $sd = 0.80$), followed by social ($m = 3.83$; $sd = 0.99$), cognitive ($m = 3.76$; $sd = 1.02$), active ($m = 3.33$; $sd = 1.13$), and creative ($m = 3.08$; $sd = 1.25$). These findings indicated that teachers tend to favor leisure activities that are less physically demanding and more restorative or relational.

The high level of passive leisure activity participation suggests that teachers frequently turn to low-effort or restful pastimes, such as watching TV, listening to music, or simply unwinding, to manage the demands of their jobs. This was consistent with the findings of Iwasaki (2007), who highlighted that passive leisure promotes mental recovery by allowing psychological detachment from work, especially for educators who deal with much emotional labor. It also supports Sonnentag and Fritz's (2020) finding that passive leisure helps replenish the emotional and cognitive reserves depleted by extended work-related stress.

In terms of social leisure engagement, teachers demonstrated a strong inclination to spend time with others through social gatherings, community events, and professional group interactions. The engagement level in this domain ($m = 3.83$) reinforces the notion that interpersonal connection serves as a buffer against burnout. According to Park et al. (2020), social connections are crucial for resilience and emotional well-being, particularly in people-oriented occupations such as teaching. Additionally, social leisure fosters a sense of support and belonging, both of which are crucial for coping with the pressures of academic settings.

The cognitive type of leisure, which includes activities that stimulate thinking and learning (e.g., watching documentaries, solving puzzles, engaging in intellectual discussion), also received an "Engaged" rating. This showed that teachers value continuous mental stimulation even outside of their professional duties. The notion that cognitively stimulating leisure promotes lifelong learning, cognitive flexibility, and less mental exhaustion is supported by Saarikallio et al. (2021).

Although active leisure was only rated as "Moderately Engaged" ($m=3.33$), it is essential area worth promoting. This relatively lower score may be attributed to time constraints, fatigue, or lack of access to recreational facilities. However, according to Warburton and Bredin (2021), engaging in regular physical activity has several advantages for overall health as well as for teachers with hectic schedules. These advantages include lowering stress, elevating mood, and boosting productivity.

Lastly, the creative domain of leisure recorded the lowest level of engagement ($m=3.08$). While still within the "Moderately Engaged" category, this suggested that teachers may have limited time, interest, or resources to participate in creative pursuits like writing, music, or arts. Nevertheless, recent research by Becker et al. (2022) and Fancourt & Finn (2019) shows that artistic expression can greatly improve emotional health, boost self-esteem, and promote personal fulfillment.

These findings underscore the importance of offering a range of recreational opportunities to foster teachers' well-being and alleviate barriers to engaging in more creative and physically demanding pursuits.

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Table 7: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Degree in terms of Frequency

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I participate in active leisure activities (e.g., sports, exercise, outdoor adventures).	3.53	1.01	High
2. I engage in passive leisure activities (e.g., watching TV, listening to music, and using social media).	4.46	0.69	High
3. I take part in social leisure activities (e.g., gatherings, outings, group events).	3.84	0.88	High
4. I engage in cognitive leisure activities (e.g., reading puzzles, learning new skills).	3.68	0.98	High
5. I participate in creative leisure activities (e.g., painting, writing, playing an instrument).	3.09	1.26	Moderate
Overall	3.72	0.96	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very High, 3.50-4.49 High, 2.50-3.49 Moderate, 1.50-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.49 Very Low

Table 7 shows that the highest-rated activity in terms of frequency was passive leisure, with a mean of 4.46 (SD = 0.69) and a verbal interpretation rating of High. This suggests that teachers often turn to passive activities, such as watching television, listening to music, or using social media, to relax. This reflected the actual situation of many teachers in Mauban South District who, after a long hour of teaching and administrative work, preferred easily accessible and low effort activities for relaxation. Sonnentag and Fritz (2020) claim that passive leisure offers both physical and psychological rest, both of which are critical for stress recovery, particularly for people in high-demand occupations like teaching.

Social leisure followed closely, with a (m=3.84; sd=0.88), also interpreted as High. Teachers appear to regularly participated in social activities such as gatherings, outings, and group events. Cognitive leisure activities, including reading puzzles, or learning new skills, were also interpreted with a High level of (m=3.68; sd=0.98). These activities not only stimulate mental faculties but also offer a sense of personal achievement and cognitive renewal. According to Saarikallio et al. (2021), cognitive leisure enhances memory, concentration, and creativity—all of which are advantageous for teachers' professional growth and effectiveness in the classroom. Active leisure activities, such as sports, exercise, and outdoor adventures, scored (m=3.53; sd=1.01), also within the High range. Despite teaching being a time-intensive profession, this result indicated that many teachers still prioritized physical activity. The results of Warburton and Bredin (2021) were corroborated by this, as they claimed that regular exercise elevates mood, lessens fatigue, and improves general well-being, especially in occupations where burnout is common. On the other hand, creative leisure activities received the lowest mean score (m=3.09; sd=1.26), falling under the Moderate category. While still practiced, these activities – such as painting, writing, or playing an instrument – may be limited by time, resources, or confidence in artistic abilities. Nonetheless, Fancourt and Finn's (2019) research demonstrated that even sporadic creative activity greatly enhances resilience, self-expression, and emotional control. A potential for enrichment and encouragement in institutional or personal settings is indicated by the comparatively lower frequency.

Based on Table 7, the overall mean score of 3.72 and standard deviation of 0.96 indicated that teachers are generally highly engaged in leisure activities across different domains. The results show that teachers have a favorable propensity to incorporate leisure into their weekly or daily schedules in order to strike a balance between their personal and professional obligations.

Table 8: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Degree in terms of Intensity

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I engage in active leisure (e.g., sports, exercise) with high energy and effort.	3.26	1.02	Moderate
2. I fully immerse myself in passive leisure activities (e.g., watching TV, listening to music).	4.16	0.86	High
3. I am highly engaged when participating in social leisure (e.g., gatherings, outings).	3.64	0.90	High
4. I deeply focus on cognitive leisure activities (e.g., reading, problem solving learning.)	3.63	0.89	High
5. I divide significant time and effort to creative (e.g., painting, music, writing).	3.12	1.08	Moderate
Overall	3.66	0.96	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very High, 3.50-4.49 High, 2.50-3.49 Moderate, 1.50-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.49 Very Low

Table 8 shows that the highest intensity was reported in passive leisure activities, such as watching television, listening to music, or engaging with digital content (m = 4.16; sd = 0.86), which is interpreted as High. This suggested that teachers often become fully immersed and emotionally invested in these activities, likely as form of mental escape or relaxation. Despite requiring little physical exertion, passive leisure activities can be profoundly calming and restorative, helping professionals manage their emotional exhaustion and recharge from the demands of their jobs (Kuykendall et al., 2018).

Social leisure activities also received a strong engagement intensity score (M = 3.64, SD = 0.96). This demonstrated how educators actively and significantly engaged in social interactions, including get-togethers, outings, and community-based activities. According to Tkach and Lyubomirsky (2021), maintaining healthy social relationships is crucial for enhancing

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psychological well-being and serving as a robust protective factor against work-related stress, particularly in emotionally demanding occupations such as teaching.

Similarly, cognitive leisure activities, such as reading, problem-solving, and learning new skills, garnered a high mean score ($m = 3.63$; $sd = 0.89$), indicating that teachers approach these activities with significant focus and mental engagement. These results align with those of O'Connor and Paunonen (2020), who found that cognitive leisure, particularly when participants are fully engaged in the activity, promotes lifelong learning and cognitive resilience.

In contrast, active leisure activities, including exercise and sports, received a low intensity rating ($m=3.26$; $sd=1.02$), categorized as Moderate. While teachers do engage in these physically demanding activities, the intensity may be influenced by factors such as energy levels, time availability, and physical health limitations. Despite the well-established health benefits of physical activity, Chang and Lee (2021) found that after extended workdays, occupational fatigue and a lack of motivation can lead to a decline in engagement intensity.

The lowest intensity was observed in creative leisure activities ($M = 3.12$, $SD = 1.08$), which is also interpreted as Moderate. This may be due to factors such as fatigue, limited free time, or lack of access to facilities, all of which are common challenges faced by public school teachers in the Mauban South District. While creative expression has therapeutic and emotional benefits, Perruzza & Kinsella (2010) pointed out that it frequently requires a quiet space, undivided time, and intrinsic motivation—factors that busy educators may find more challenging to access.

The analysis of the level of leisure engagement among teachers in terms of intensity reveals an overall mean score of 3.56 with a standard deviation of 0.96, which falls under the category of “High.” This suggests that when engaging in various recreational activities, teachers generally exhibit a significant level of psychological and physical involvement or exertion. While active and creative engagements may be less intense due to internal and external constraints, passive, social, and cognitive pursuits appear to offer a more immersive experience.

Table 9: Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Degree in terms of Quality

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I feel more energized and motivated after participating in leisure activities.	4.18	0.85	High
2. I enjoy leisure activities that help me relax and unwind after a stressful day.	4.54	0.64	Very High
3. I feel socially connected and supported through my leisure activities.	4.18	0.76	High
4. I feel mentally refreshed and recharged after engaging in leisure activities.	4.36	0.75	High
5. I feel that my leisure activities contribute to my personal growth or self-development.	4.39	0.75	High
Overall	4.33	0.75	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very High, 3.50-4.49 High, 2.50-3.49 Moderate, 1.50-2.49 Low, 1.00-1.49 Very Low

Table 9 presents the level of leisure engagement of teachers based on quality. The highest-rated indicator was “I enjoy leisure activities that help me relax and unwind after a stressful day” with a ($m=4.54$; $sd=0.64$), which falls under the “High” category. This indicates that teachers are effectively utilizing leisure as a coping mechanism to alleviate stress. This result is consistent with a study by Newman et al. (2014), which found that leisure activities emphasizing relaxation are highly linked to reduced stress and improved emotional regulation, especially in high-pressure occupations such as teaching.

The indicators “I feel energized and motivated after participating in leisure activities” and “I feel socially connected and supported through my leisure activities” both scored a mean of 4.18, with standard deviations of 0.85 and 0.76, respectively, indicating a strong level of engagement. Both have a verbal interpretation of High.

These findings demonstrate the social and restorative benefits of leisure activities. Quality leisure improves intrinsic motivation and cultivates interpersonal relationships, both of which are critical for teachers' resilience and long-term job satisfaction (Caldwell, 2005). The statement “I feel mentally refreshed and recharged after engaging in leisure activities,” had a mean of ($m=4.36$; $sd=0.75$) reflecting that cognitive restoration is a significant benefit derived from quality leisure. This confirmed Pressman et al.'s (2022) findings that quality leisure, particularly that which involves creative expression, mindfulness, or exposure to nature, greatly improves cognitive functioning and lessens mental exhaustion. Similarly, the indicator “I feel that my leisure activities contribute to my personal growth or self-development” scored a ($m=4.39$; $sd=0.75$), reinforcing the idea that teachers perceived their leisure as meaningful and developmental. Tinsley and Eldredge (2005) assert that good leisure is both transformative and recreational, offering opportunities for education, introspection, and goal achievement.

Table 9 presents an overall mean of 4.33 and a standard deviation of 0.75, interpreted as “High.” This suggests that teachers view their leisure activities as generally of high quality, which enhances their general well-being and sense of fulfillment in life.

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Table 10: Summary Table on Level of Leisure Engagement as to its Degree

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Frequency	3.72	0.96	High
Intensity	3.56	0.96	High
Quality	4.33	0.75	High
Overall	3.87	0.89	High

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very High, 3.50-4.49 High, 2.50-3.49 Moderate, 1.50- 2.49 Low, 1.00-1.49 Very Low

Table 10 shows that among the three dimensions, quality had the highest mean of (m=4.33; sd=0.75), falling into the “High” category. This highlights that the leisure activities teachers engage in are perceived as highly fulfilling, restorative, and personally meaningful. According to Newman, Tay, and Diener (2014), stress recovery, life satisfaction, and positive emotional experiences are all closely linked to high-quality leisure. For teachers, this means that their leisure activities are not only enjoyable but also make a deep contribution to their emotional and mental well-being. The frequency of engagement had a mean score of (m=3.72; sd=0.96), also interpreted as “High.” This showed that teachers participate in leisure activities on a regular basis. Meanwhile, the intensity of engagement recorded a mean of (m=3.56; sd=0.96), which is on the lower end of the “High” category. Despite their active involvement in leisure activities, teachers may not always require a lot of energy or concentration for their work. Making this decision could be a calculated move to save energy for work-related obligations. Since excessive stimulation can become draining, particularly for individuals with demanding workloads, Caldwell (2005) asserts that striking a balance between low- and high-intensity leisure activities is crucial for long-term well-being.

Based on the data presented in Table 10, the overall level of leisure engagement in terms of its degree yielded a mean score of 3.87 and a standard deviation of 0.89, which is interpreted as “High.” This implies that educators engage in leisure activities on a regular basis, put forth a great deal of effort in doing so, and reap substantial emotional and personal rewards from their participation.

Table 11: Level of Sustainable Well-Being in terms of Emotional

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I feel satisfied and fulfilled in my teaching profession.	4.26	0.68	Great Extent
2. I can effectively manage stress related to teaching responsibilities.	4.26	0.67	Great Extent
3. I feel emotionally supported by my colleagues and administration.	4.12	0.74	Great Extent
4. I can maintain a healthy work-life balance.	4.16	0.77	Great Extent
5. I feel valued and appreciated for my efforts as a teacher.	4.14	0.86	Great Extent
Overall	4.19	0.75	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50- 2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not At All

Table 11 shows that, as stated in indicator 1, “I feel satisfied and fulfilled in my teaching profession (m=4.26; sd=0.68) received one of the highest mean scores, suggesting that teacher generally derive significant satisfaction and fulfillment from their profession. This is consistent with research by Benevene et al. (2023), who highlighted that teachers who felt their work had a significant and lasting impact were more likely to report feeling emotionally well and being fulfilled in their careers. Indicator 2, “I can effectively manage stress related to teaching responsibilities (m=4.26; sd 0.67). To preserve long-term emotional well-being, teachers reported having a strong ability to manage stress related to their jobs. Effective stress management among educators is linked to improved classroom performance and decreased burnout, particularly in high-pressure learning environments, according to Kim and Asbury (2020).

However, indicator 3, “I feel emotionally supported by my colleagues and administration (m=4.12; sd=0.74). This result indicated a high level of perceived emotional support within the school environment. Supportive workplace relationships are crucial buffers against occupational stress. According to recent research by Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2021), administrative and collegial support are important predictors of teachers' emotional resilience and job satisfaction.

Moreover, indicator 4, “I can maintain healthy work-life balance,” (m=4.16, SD=0.77). The majority of teachers feel capable of managing their professional and personal lives, reflecting a strong sense of balance. This is in line with the findings of Wei et al. (2022), who observed that in the teaching profession, work-life balance is positively correlated with job satisfaction and reduced emotional exhaustion. Lastly, indicator 5, “I feel valued and appreciated for my effort as a teacher” (m=4.14, sd=0.86). Teachers also reported feeling appreciated, which fosters emotional security and motivation. Collie et al. (2012) assert that a teacher's

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emotional health, sense of purpose, and sense of belonging are improved when they receive praise from students, peers, and administrators.

Based on the results shown in Table 11, all five indicators scoring above 4.00 are rated as Great Extent. The overall level of emotional well-being among teachers in Mauban South District yielded a mean score of 4.19 and a standard deviation of 0.75, indicating that teachers experience emotional well-being to a Great Extent. This proved that the majority of the study's teachers experience emotional stability, support, and job satisfaction.

Table 12: Level of Sustainable Well-Being in terms of Physical

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I feel physically healthy and capable of handling my daily teaching tasks.	4.32	0.65	Great Extent
2. I get enough rest and sleep to function well during the school day.	3.74	0.97	Great Extent
3. I engage in regular physical activity or exercise to maintain my well-being.	3.55	1.01	Great Extent
4. I have enough energy to perform my teaching duties effectively.	4.21	0.66	Great Extent
5. I maintain a balanced and nutritious diet that supports my overall health.	3.83	0.86	Great Extent
Overall	3.93	0.83	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50-2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not At All

Table 12 shows that among the indicators, the statement “I feel physically healthy and capable of handling my daily teaching task” received the highest mean score ($m=4.32$; $sd=0.65$), suggesting that most teachers feel physically capable of performing their duties. According to Skaalvic and Skaalvic (2021), teachers who have a positive view of their physical capabilities report feeling less stressed and more satisfied with their jobs, which acts as a protective factor against burnout. Furthermore, a teacher's physical capacity frequently determines how well they perform in their roles, underscoring the significance of maintaining good health for long-term professional success. The indicators of rest and sleep ($m=3.74$; $sd=0.97$). A substantial number of teachers report adequate rest, which is crucial for mental clarity and physical resilience. The standard deviation shows moderate variability, indicating not all teachers experience this consistently. According to Wei and Ye (2022), getting enough sleep is strongly linked to less emotional exhaustion and improved productivity at work. Lack of rest, in contrast, has been shown to heighten stress and increase health risks. Physical activity ($m = 3.55$; $sd = 1.01$) also demonstrated high engagement in terms of physical well-being, although these scores were slightly lower compared to other indicators. The relatively lower mean for physical activity suggested that while teachers may feel physically healthy and energized, the ability to engage in regular physical activity may be limited due to work demands. According to Pressman et al. (2022), physical activity significantly reduces stress and improves overall well-being, particularly among professionals in high-demand occupations, such as teaching. Additionally, while teachers reported feeling they had enough energy to perform their duties effectively (mean = 4.21, SD = 0.66), the mean score for maintaining a balanced and nutritious diet (mean = 3.83, SD = 0.86) suggested room for improvement in terms of dietary habits.

Thus, the findings of this study highlight the importance for teachers to prioritize their physical health by exercising regularly, getting sufficient sleep, and maintaining a balanced diet, in order to enhance their overall job satisfaction and productivity.

The level of sustainable well-being in terms of Physical indicated that teachers generally experience a high degree of physical well-being, as reflected in the overall mean of 3.93 and a standard deviation of 0.83. While all indicators are interpreted with Great Extent of physical well-being, the study also reveals areas of potential improvement, particularly in the domains of physical activity and dietary habit. To improve teachers' physical health, organizations should think about introducing wellness initiatives, scheduling physical activity, and offering dietary advice.

Table 13: Level of Sustainable Well-Being in terms of Social

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I feel connected and supported by my colleagues.	4.19	0.78	Great Extent
2. I have positive and meaningful relationships with my students.	4.44	0.63	Great Extent
3. I feel valued and respected by my school administration and peers.	4.26	0.76	Great Extent
4. I actively participate in school-related social activities and events.	4.26	0.69	Great Extent
5. I maintain a healthy balance between my social life and professional responsibilities.	4.21	0.71	Great Extent
Overall	4.27	0.72	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50-2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not At All

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Table 13 shows that the indicator with the highest mean score was “I have positive and meaningful relationships with my students” ($m = 4.44$; $sd = 0.63$), suggesting that strong teacher-student relationships are a cornerstone of teachers’ well-being. This result aligns with recent research by Martin et al. (2023), which highlights the benefits of fostering a caring and respectful relationship with students for improved teacher morale, reduced burnout, and enhanced classroom dynamics. In addition to improving students' academic performance, these relationships give teachers a sense of fulfillment and internal motivation. Other indicators, such as “I feel valued and respected by my school administration and peers,” and “I actively participate in school-related social activities and events,” both received high mean scores of ($m=4.26$) and ($sd=0.78$) and ($sd=0.69$), respectively. Demonstrating that recognition and involvement in the school community significantly contribute to social well-being. Zee & Koomen (2016) state that teachers' job satisfaction and retention rates typically increase when they perceive that their superiors and peers value them. Additionally, teachers feel more integrated and supported when they participate in school activities because it creates a sense of community and connection. The indicator “I maintain a healthy balance between my social life and professional responsibilities,” ($m=4.21$; $sd=0.71$) reflects that teachers are capable of managing both personal and work-related relationships effectively – a key trait of well-rounded social well-being. According to Day and Gu (2014), who noted that educators with strong social support and clear boundaries typically report higher levels of resilience and life satisfaction, this balance is essential.

Meanwhile, the indicator “I feel connected and supported by my colleagues” ($m = 4.19$; $sd = 0.78$) highlights the value of peer support, which has been proven to be a buffer against occupational stress. According to White et al. (2022), collegial support networks are crucial for emotional control and sustaining teaching zeal in educational environments.

Table 13 shows that all of five indicators had a verbal interpretation of Great Extent. The level of sustainable well-being in terms of social reveals that teachers experience a high degree of social well-being, with an overall mean score of 4.27 and a standard deviation of 0.72, indicating responses to a Great Extent.

The findings indicated that teachers are engaged and supported in society, which enhances their general sustainable well-being. The high degree of social well-being is a reflection of how important it is to build meaningful relationships, get recognition from school administrators, and encourage active participation in the social aspects of the school setting. To maintain a teaching staff that is healthy, driven, and socially connected, educational institutions should keep fostering a culture of cooperation and acknowledgment in light of these findings.

Table 14: Level of Sustainable Well-Being in terms of Workplace

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher...</i>			
1. I feel safe and comfortable in my work environment.	4.33	0.73	Great Extent
2. I receive adequate support from my school administration.	4.04	0.80	Great Extent
3. I have a manageable workload that allows me to have a healthy work-life balance.	4.20	0.80	Great Extent
4. I have access to the necessary resources and materials to teach effectively.	4.06	0.80	Great Extent
5. I have opportunities for professional growth and career development.	4.14	0.77	Great Extent
Overall	4.15	0.78	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50-2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not at All

Table 14 shows that the highest-rated indicator was “I feel safe and comfortable in my work environment” ($m = 4.33$, $sd = 0.73$), underscoring the importance of both physical and psychological safety in educational settings. A key component of employee well-being is workplace safety, and when educators feel safe in their surroundings, they are better able to concentrate on teaching and student growth (Bakker & de Vries, 2021). Additionally, Skaalvik & Skaalvik (2011) highlighted that a secure and trustworthy school environment greatly improves teacher well-being and reduces emotional exhaustion. Similarly, the indicator “I have a manageable workload that allows me to have a healthy work-life balance” ($m=4.20$; $sd=0.80$) also received a high score, reflecting that teachers find their responsibilities reasonable and not overly burdensome. According to Sonnentag & Fritz (2007), recuperation and disengagement from work are crucial strategies for preserving well-being. This process is made possible by a controlled workload. Furthermore, the indicator “I have opportunities for professional growth and career development ($m=4.14$; $sd=0.77$) indicates that respondents feel their professional advancement is supported, contributing positively to their sense of purpose and long-term well-being. According to Fritiz et al. (2019), learning and mastery opportunities are essential psychological needs that support long-term job engagement and personal fulfillment. Moreover, the indicator “I have access to the necessary resources and materials to teach effectively ($m=4.06$; $sd=0.80$) highlights that teachers feel equipped with the tools needed to perform their tasks, which is vital for quality instruction. According to Warburton and Bredin (2019), having access to both intellectual and physical resources is essential for reducing stress levels and maintaining professional involvement in the education sector. Lastly, support from school administration emerged as a crucial component with the item, “I receive adequate support from my school administration,” scoring a mean of ($m=4.04$; $sd=0.80$). According to Demir et al. (2022), a significant predictor of

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teachers' resilience and professional well-being under pressure is robust administrative support. It is more probable that teachers will perform well and stay involved in their jobs if they feel that the leadership is supporting them. All of these indicators received a verbal interpretation of Great Extent.

The level of sustainable well-being in terms of the workplace provides a significant understanding of how conducive the school environment is to the overall well-being of teachers. In this study, the overall mean score of 4.15 with a standard deviation of 0.78 indicates that teachers experience workplace well-being to a Great Extent, suggesting a positive and supportive working environment.

Table 15: Level of Sustainable Well-Being in terms of Societal

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
<i>As a teacher ...</i>			
1. I feel that teaching is a respected and valued profession in society.	4.54	0.60	Very Great Extent
2. I receive fair and adequate compensation for my work as a teacher.	4.06	0.88	Great Extent
3. I have opportunities to engage in community activities related to education.	4.15	0.77	Great Extent
4. I receive support from parents and the broader community in my teaching role.	4.14	0.78	Great Extent
5. I believe that the government and policymakers prioritize the well-being of teachers.	3.82	1.04	Great Extent
Overall	4.14	0.81	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50-2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not At All

Table 15 shows that teachers perceive their societal well-being to a Great Extent, with an overall mean score of 4.14 and a standard deviation of 0.81. Among the indicators, the highest-rated item is the belief that “teaching is a respected and valued profession in society ($m=4.54$; $sd=0.60$), indicating that most teachers strongly feel appreciated in their societal role. This is consistent with research by Sahlberg (2021), who highlighted the important role that societal recognition plays in teachers' sense of purpose and professional identity. In a similar vein, Day and Qing (2009) observed that teachers' emotional fortitude and commitment to their work are enhanced when they perceive that society values them.

The indicator related to “fair and adequate compensation scored lower ($m=4.06$; $sd=0.88$) but still falls under the interpretation of Great Extent. This suggests moderate satisfaction with compensation, although with greater variability in responses. According to Demir et al. (2019), job satisfaction and well-being among educators are significantly influenced by their perception of fairness in pay and benefits.

In items of “opportunities for community engagement ($m=4.15$; $sd=0.77$) and support from parents and the broader community ($m=4.14$; $sd=0.78$), the results suggest that teachers feel involved and supported beyond the classroom. Additionally, Fancourt and Finn (2019) highlighted that community involvement fosters social connection and a sense of belonging, and that these factors both improve psychological resilience.

The lowest mean is in the data, though still within Great Extent range, relates to the belief that “government and policymakers prioritize teacher well-being ($m=3.82$; $sd=1.04$). This relatively lower score, coupled with higher variability, indicates a less consistent perception of policy support.

Overall, the statistics show that societal factors, especially community involvement, support, and recognition, have a significant impact on teachers' long-term well-being. There is still room for improvement, though, in areas like policy-level prioritization and compensation.

Table 16: Summary Table on Level of Sustainable Well-Being

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Interpretation
Emotional	4.19	0.75	Great Extent
Physical	3.93	0.83	Great Extent
Social	4.27	0.72	Great Extent
Workplace	4.15	0.78	Great Extent
Societal	4.14	0.81	Great Extent
Overall	4.14	0.78	Great Extent

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Very Great Extent, 3.50-4.49 Great Extent, 2.50-3.49 Moderate Extent, 1.50-2.49 Low Extent, 1.00-1.49 Not At All

Table 16 presents the summary of the respondents' level of sustainable well-being across five key indicators: emotional, physical, social, workplace, and societal dimensions. The results show that all indicators fall within the range of Great Extent based on the computed means. Specifically, social well-being obtained the highest mean score ($m = 4.27$; $sd = 0.72$), indicating that teachers experience a strong sense of connectedness, support, and social integration. This is in line with Keyes' (1998) model of social

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well-being, which places a strong emphasis on the value of social connection and belonging. Emotional well-being followed closely ($m=4.19$; $sd=0.75$), indicating that teachers typically feel happy and satisfied with their lives, which is in line with Diener et al. (2010)'s findings that emotional stability plays a major role in long-term happiness. Workplace well-being ($m=4.15$; $sd=0.78$) and societal well-being ($m=4.14$; $sd=0.81$) were also rated to a Great Extent, implying that the teachers perceive their professional environment and societal contributions as meaningful and fulfilling. Lastly, physical well-being received the lowest mean ($m=3.93$; $sd=0.83$) among the five, though still within the Great Extent range. This suggests that while teachers are generally physically healthy, this dimension may be slightly less prioritized or more variable.

Overall, the composite mean ($m=4.14$; $sd=0.78$) reflects a high level of sustainable well-being among the participants, supporting the findings of Dodge et al. (2012), who contend that people can attain sustainable well-being by maintaining balance in their personal, social, and professional lives. These findings underscore the intricate relationship between well-being and teaching, suggesting that enhanced well-being outcomes may lead to increased resilience, engagement, and effectiveness.

Table 17: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy

Indicators	Self Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
<i>As a teacher</i>									
1. I demonstrate a deep understanding of the subject matter being taught	4.57	0.54	O	4.65	0.56	O	4.58	0.54	O
2. I integrate concepts from different subject to enhance student learning	4.49	0.58	VS	4.62	0.60	O	4.51	0.60	O
3. I use a variety of teaching strategies to enhance students' reading and numeracy skills	4.49	0.52	VS	4.64	0.61	O	4.57	0.58	O
4. I encourage students to analyze, evaluate, and create new ideas in their learning	4.58	0.52	O	4.59	0.67	O	4.58	0.60	O
5. I effectively use Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English in defining lessons to facilitate teaching and learning	4.64	0.50	O	4.72	0.54	O	4.60	0.60	O
Overall	4.55	0.56	O	4.64	0.60	O	4.57	0.58	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O); 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS); 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S); 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US); 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI)

Table 17 presents the assessment of teachers' performance based on the core domain of Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, evaluated through three lenses: self-evaluation, student ratings, and peer evaluation. Across all five indicators, the overall weighted means from all raters fall within the "Outstanding" range (4.50-5.00), indicating a consistently high level of teaching proficiency among the participating teachers.

Self-rating yielded an overall mean of $m = 4.55$ ($SD = 0.56$), indicating that teachers perceive themselves as highly competent in their subject matter and pedagogical approaches. Teachers rated themselves particularly high in facilitating critical and creative thinking (mean = 4.58) and effective multilingual instruction (mean = 4.64), reinforcing their confidence in key pedagogical skills. These results are consistent with a study by Shulman (1987), who highlighted the importance of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK), or the fusion of pedagogy and content, for successful instruction. Teachers are more likely to create engaging learning experiences when they feel they have a firm grasp of both the subject matter and the teaching methodology.

From the students' perspective, the overall mean was even higher ($m = 4.64$; $sd = 0.60$), indicating that students highly recognize their teachers' competence. The highest rating was observed in the effective use of Mother Tongue, Filipino, and English ($m = 4.72$), suggesting that students benefit from teachers' capacity to shift between languages to improve comprehension and engagement. The results of Cummins (2000), who promoted the cognitive benefits of multilingual education in improving learning outcomes, are corroborated by this. Additionally, students gave their teachers high marks for using a variety of tactics to advance literacy and numeracy ($m = 4.64$), in line with Vygotsky's (1978) hypothesis that academic development and higher-order thinking are fostered by student-centered, scaffolded instruction.

Peer evaluations yielded an overall mean of $m = 4.57$ ($SD = 0.58$), closely aligning with both self-ratings and student ratings. Peers particularly commended the promotion of critical thinking and the use of varied strategies (e.g., $m = 4.59$ for encouraging analysis and creativity; $m = 4.57$ for teaching strategies). These assessments support Bandura's (1997) social learning theory, which holds that peer collaboration and observation improve the quality of instruction, and they demonstrate a collegial recognition of professional standards.

Among individual indicators, the integration (Indicator 2) was rated slightly lower across all raters, although still within the Very Satisfactory to Outstanding range. This may suggest a potential area for professional development – enhancing interdisciplinary teaching – which is increasingly vital in 21st century education. Integrated curriculum approaches, as proposed by Beane (1997), encourage greater comprehension and practical application, but they also require careful preparation and support.

Overall, the consistently high ratings from self, student, and peers indicate a robust level of teaching performance, particularly in applying content knowledge through effective pedagogy. These results affirm the importance of continuous professional development in both subject mastery and pedagogical innovation to sustain excellence in classroom teaching. Effective teaching is

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firmly anchored in the interaction of teachers' knowledge, their teaching style, and their relationship with students, as demonstrated by Darling-Hammond et al. (2017).

Table 18: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Learning Environment

Indicators As a teacher...	Self Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. I ensure that the classroom is safe, free from distractions, and conducive to learning.	4.53	0.62	O	4.61	0.63	O	4.49	0.62	VS
2. I establish clear classroom rules and expectations that respect students' cultural backgrounds.	4.60	0.66	O	4.76	0.52	O	4.57	0.60	O
3. I engage students in activities that promote respect for diverse linguistic and learning backgrounds.	4.58	0.57	O	4.60	0.60	O	4.63	0.58	O
4. I modify teaching strategies to meet the unique needs and identities of my students.	4.55	0.64	O	4.68	0.58	O	4.58	0.59	O
5. I create a culturally responsive learning environment that promotes inclusivity.	4.48	0.59	VS	4.56	0.69	O	4.54	0.62	O
Overall	4.54	0.58	O	4.64	0.62	O	4.56	0.60	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI)

Table 18 presents the assessment of teaching performance focused on the domain of Learning Environment, as rated by the teachers themselves, their students, and their peers. The overall results across all raters indicate an “Outstanding” performance level, with means of $m = 4.54$ ($sd = 0.58$) for self-assessment, $m = 4.65$ ($sd = 0.62$) from students, and $m = 4.56$ ($sd = 0.60$) from peers. These ratings highlight the consistent ability of teachers to create inclusive, respectful, and adaptable classroom environments that foster learning.

From the self-assessment, teachers perceive themselves as particularly strong in establishing clear classroom rules and expectations respectful of students' cultural backgrounds ($m=4.60$), and in modifying teaching strategies to cater to diverse student needs ($m=4.55$). These findings are consistent with Gay's (2010) theory of culturally responsive teaching, which highlights how crucial it is to value and acknowledge students' cultural identities in instructional design and classroom management. Moreover, teachers reported slightly lower – but still high – confidence in promoting culturally inclusive learning environments ($m=4.48$), indicating a possible area for continued growth in equity-oriented practices.

Student's ratings, which have the highest among the three groups ($m=4.64$), reinforce the positive impact of teacher's efforts. They especially acknowledged the clarity of classroom rules and respect for cultural backgrounds ($m=4.76$) and the individualized adaptation of instruction ($m=4.68$). These results are consistent with Hattie's (2009) research, which highlighted the strong correlation between academic success and a secure and encouraging learning environment. Nieto's (2010) emphasis on the socio-emotional and cultural aspects of learning as crucial to student engagement and performance is also in line with the strong student perception of inclusivity and respect in the classroom.

From the peer perspectives, the mean score of ($m=4.56$) confirms a professional consensus on the teachers' effective classroom management and responsiveness to diversity. Notably, Indicator 1 – ensuring a safe and distraction – free environment – received the lowest peer score ($m=4.49$), slightly dipping into the Very Satisfactory range. Peers may have noticed subtle differences in the physical or emotional classroom environment that students may not be able to see or the teacher may not be aware of. As Manzano (2003) noted, peer review is crucial for enhancing instructional strategies that self-assessment alone might not be able to address.

In summary, the information confirms that educators are effectively creating inclusive, safe, and culturally sensitive learning environments. This strength has been confirmed by several assessors, demonstrating a comprehensive and reliable use of best practices in establishing a productive learning environment. Focused efforts on ongoing physical and emotional classroom condition improvement, particularly as perceived by peers, can further strengthen performance and guarantee that excellence is maintained in all areas of the learning environment.

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Table 19: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Diversity of Learners

Indicators	Self-Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. I recognize that students have different learning styles and abilities.	4.66	0.47	O	4.47	0.77	VS	4.53	0.63	O
2. I used a variety of instructional materials and technologies to meet diverse learning needs.	4.46	0.58	VS	4.54	0.74	O	4.55	0.62	O
3. I provide differentiated instruction to accommodate students varying learning paces.	4.47	0.61	VS	4.54	0.81	O	4.60	0.61	O
4. I encourage student participation and ensure equal learning opportunities.	4.58	0.56	O	4.50	0.74	O	4.53	0.64	O
5. I promote an inclusive classroom where all students feel valued and respected.	4.66	0.52	O	4.72	0.57	O	4.48	0.68	VS
Overall	4.57	0.55	O	4.55	0.72	O	4.54	0.64	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI)

Table 19 presents the level of teaching performance in the domain of Diversity of Learners, as assessed by teachers (self), students, and peers. All three groups rated teacher performance within the “Outstanding” range overall, with means of $m = 4.57$ ($sd = 0.55$) for self-assessment, $m = 4.55$ ($sd = 0.72$) from students, and $m = 4.54$ ($sd = 0.64$) from peers. These results indicate that teachers consistently demonstrate effective strategies in recognizing and addressing students’ diverse learning needs.

According to the teachers’ self-assessment, the highest ratings were given to recognizing different learning styles and abilities ($m = 4.66$) and promoting inclusivity, where all students feel valued ($m = 4.66$). These results align with Tomlinson's (2014) research, which highlights that two essential components of successful, equitable teaching are identifying learner diversity and implementing differentiated instruction. However, slightly lower ratings were noted in using varied instructional materials and providing differentiated instruction ($m=4.46$) and ($m=4.47$), which, while still “Very Satisfactory,” may suggest areas where teachers feel improvement is possible in instructional delivery and pacing adjustments.

Students, on the other hand, provided their highest score for promoting an inclusive and respectful classroom ($m = 4.72$), highlighting how students positively experience their teachers’ inclusivity efforts. This supports the multicultural education theory of Banks (2015), which posits that students' engagement and academic performance are significantly enhanced when they feel valued and acknowledged. Interestingly, students gave the lowest score to the recognition of different learning styles ($m=4.47$), the only indicator rated as “Very Satisfactory.” This implies that students may still feel that their particular learning preferences are not always recognized or taken into consideration, even if teachers think they differentiate instruction effectively.

Peers rated teacher performance highly, especially in providing differentiated instruction ($m = 4.60$) and using varied instructional strategies ($m = 4.55$), which supports the notion that colleagues perceive teachers as professionally adaptive and responsive. However, the promotion of inclusive classrooms received a slightly lower peer rating ($m = 4.48$), “Very Satisfactory,” which may indicate that while efforts toward inclusivity are recognized, there is room for further refinement.

The convergence of rater ratings, particularly those with consistently high overall means, confirms how well teachers handle the diversity of their students. It showcases the implementation of key strategies, including inclusive classroom procedures, differentiated instruction, and the utilization of technology and various resources to meet students' diverse needs.

In conclusion, the data confirm that educators are doing a great job of addressing the diversity of learners through inclusive, courteous, and flexible teaching methods. Although all metrics are in the Outstanding or Very Satisfactory range, specific adjustments to enhance student awareness of learning styles and promote inclusive classroom dynamics, as assessed by peers, could further improve teaching performance in this crucial area.

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Table 20: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Curriculum and Planning

Indicators	Self Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
1. I align lesson plans with curriculum standards and learning competencies.	4.65	0.51	O	4.61	0.61	O	4.61	0.57	O
2. I prepare well-structured lesson plans that meet learning objectives.	4.54	0.59	O	4.65	0.61	O	4.59	0.56	O
3. I incorporate innovative teaching strategies to enhance learning.	4.43	0.64	VS	4.52	0.73	O	4.51	0.63	O
4. I use real-life examples and contextualized learning materials.	4.63	0.53	O	4.56	0.66	O	4.59	0.59	O
5. I plan activities that foster collaboration and active student engagement.	4.58	0.56	O	4.61	0.65	O	4.53	0.63	O
Overall	4.57	0.57	O	4.59	0.65	O	4.57	0.60	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI)

Table 20 outlines the level of teaching performance of educators in the area of Curriculum and Planning, based on evaluations from the teachers themselves, their students, and their peers. The overall mean scores from all three groups – self (m=4.57; sd=0.57), students (m=4.59; sd=0.65), and peers (m=4.57; sd=0.60) – fall under the “Outstanding” category. These consistently high scores demonstrate the teachers' proficiency in creating and implementing lesson plans that meet curriculum standards and utilizing engagement and contextual learning strategies.

Teachers rated themselves highest on aligning lesson plans with curriculum standards and competencies (m = 4.65), followed by contextualizing lessons using real-life examples (m = 4.63) and fostering collaboration through planned activities (m = 4.58). This self-perception demonstrates their dedication to both practical application and strategic curriculum implementation. These results lend support to Tyler's (1949) seminal model of curriculum development, which emphasizes the importance of aligning instructional strategies and assessments with learning objectives. The relatively lower self-rating on incorporating innovative strategies (m=4.43) “Very Satisfactory,” may suggest a recognition of the need for continued professional development in integrating novel, technology-based, or student-centered pedagogies.

From the students' perspective, ratings were equally high, with the highest scores given to well-structured lesson planning (mean = 4.65) and alignment with curriculum standards (mean = 4.61). Students also valued the integration of collaborative and engaging activities (M = 4.61) – an essential component of active learning. Students' high regard for real-life applications (m = 4.56) also aligns with constructivist learning theory, which advocates for contextualized instruction to make learning more meaningful.

Peers, who are often in the best position to evaluate technical and pedagogical rigor, rated all indicators in the Outstanding range, with lesson alignment (m = 4.61) and the use of contextual materials (m = 4.59) as the highest. Their slightly lower ratings on collaborative activities (m = 4.53) and innovation (m = 4.51) suggest that while teachers are meeting core instructional standards, there is room for enhancing creativity and collaboration in planning. Curriculum planning in the twenty-first century needs to go beyond traditional instruction to include technology, student voice, and critical thinking—areas where ongoing improvement is advantageous, claim Ornstein and Hunkins (2017).

The fact that all rater groups consistently received high scores shows that teachers are successfully carrying out the crucial duties of curriculum alignment, structure planning, and practical application. The somewhat lower innovation scores, especially from the teacher, however, indicate that more dynamic, student-driven, and technologically advanced approaches must be incorporated over time.

The findings conclude that teachers exhibit exceptional curriculum and planning performance, with a solid basis in establishing student engagement, contextualizing content, and aligning instruction with standards. It would further enhance classroom instruction and promote deeper student learning if creative and cooperative strategies were continuously improved, as evidenced by both self- and peer assessments.

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Table 21: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Assessment and Reporting

Indicators	Self/Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
As a teacher...									
1. I use different types of assessment to measure students' learning progress.	4.59	0.50	O	4.54	0.65	O	4.57	0.64	O
2. I provide timely and constructive feedback to students regarding their performance.	4.46	0.58	VS	4.69	0.58	O	4.53	0.62	O
3. I analyze assessment results to improve instructional practices.	4.45	0.58	VS	4.62	0.61	O	4.57	0.57	O
4. I communicate students' progress clearly to parents/guardians.	4.52	0.58	O	4.57	0.75	O	4.61	0.57	O
5. I ensure fairness and objectivity in grading and reporting students' performance.	4.69	0.49	O	4.56	0.71	O	4.61	0.55	O
Overall	4.54	0.56	O	4.60	0.66	O	4.58	0.59	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs improvement (NI)

Table 21 presents the teachers' level of performance in Assessment and Reporting, as rated by themselves, their students, and their peers. The overall mean score across the three groups – self (m=4.54; sd=0.56), students (m=4.60; sd=0.66), and peers (m=4.58; sd=0.59) – all fall within the “Outstanding” category (4.50 – 5.00), indicating a high level of proficiency in the assessment process, from administering various assessment types to grading and feedback mechanisms.

Teachers rated themselves particularly high on ensuring fairness and objectivity in grading (m = 4.69), followed by the use of diverse assessment types (m = 4.59), reflecting their strong sense of ethical responsibility and commitment to accurately measuring student performance. However, slightly lower scores were given in analyzing assessment data (m = 4.45) and providing timely feedback (m = 4.46), both of which were marked as “Very Satisfactory.” This implies that although teachers are competent assessors, they could do better in terms of providing timely feedback and leveraging data to inform instruction—two essential elements of formative assessment practices (Black & Wiliam, 1998).

Students consistently rated their teachers highly, particularly in terms of feedback (m=4.69) and the communication of progress (m=4.57), affirming that learners feel well-informed and supported. The focus on feedback confirms the findings of Hattie et al. (2007), who found that feedback is one of the most potent factors influencing student achievement. The high student score on assessment analysis (m = 4.62) also reflects their perceptions that teachers make instructional adjustments based on results, which aligns with effective assessment-for-learning strategies.

Peers gave outstanding ratings on most indicators, with the highest ratings for fairness in grading (M = 4.61) and communication with parents (M = 4.61). As emphasized in Guskey's (2003) model of effective grading practices, this highlights a common professional culture that values openness, moral reporting, and parental participation—all of which are crucial for a comprehensive assessment system. Notably, peers also rated data analysis for instructional improvement highly (m = 4.57), suggesting that teachers are perceived by their colleagues as reflective practitioners who use assessment to inform their pedagogy. The results from all three sources collectively confirm that teachers demonstrate exceptional proficiency in reporting and assessment, with a focus on communication, feedback, and fairness. The teachers' own somewhat lower scores in the feedback and data analysis categories, however, highlight a need for professional development centered on timely, formative feedback and data-driven instruction—two crucial components of improving student learning outcomes in accordance with contemporary assessment frameworks (OECD, 2013).

Table 22: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement

Indicators	Self/Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
As a teacher...									
1. I build a strong relationship with parents and guardians to support student learning.	4.44	0.69	VS	4.49	0.71	VS	4.63	0.53	O
2. I engage with the wider school community to facilitate student development.	4.31	0.66	VS	4.64	0.68	O	4.64	0.54	O
3. I collaborate with colleagues to improve teaching practices.	4.54	0.56	O	4.60	0.68	O	4.53	0.62	O
4. I participate in school and community activities that enhance education.	4.48	0.58	VS	4.68	0.59	O	4.53	0.62	O
5. I encourage community involvement in student learning initiatives.	4.44	0.65	VS	4.73	0.56	O	4.61	0.60	O
Overall	4.44	0.63	VS	4.63	0.62	O	4.58	0.58	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs improvement (NI)

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Table 22 presents the level of teaching performance in terms of Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, based on assessments from self, teachers, Students, and Peers. The overall mean ratings are Very Satisfactory for teachers' self-evaluation ($m = 4.44$, $sd = 0.63$), but Outstanding from both students ($m = 4.63$, $sd = 0.62$) and peers ($m = 4.59$, $sd = 0.58$). This variation suggests that although educators hold a modest opinion of their community engagement initiatives, their peers and students have a more favorable view.

For teachers' self-assessment, indicators such as "I build strong relationships with parents and guardians" ($m=4.44$) and "I encourage community involvement in student learning initiatives" ($m=4.44$) received "Very Satisfactory" marks. This may be an indication of the difficulties some educators face in developing enduring and meaningful relationships with families and community members due to time constraints, communication challenges, or socioeconomic disparities. According to Epstein's (2001) framework of school-family-community partnerships, practical cooperation necessitates institutional support and structured strategies in addition to individual effort.

Interestingly, students rated all indicators as "Outstanding," particularly in areas involving wider community and parental involvement, such as "I encourage community involvement" ($m=4.73$) and "I participate in school and community activities" ($m=4.68$). These findings suggest that students are aware of and benefit from their teachers' involvement outside the classroom. This aligns with Sheldon and Epstein's (2005) assertion that improved support networks lead to increased student motivation and performance when educators involve the community.

Peers also gave mostly "Outstanding" ratings, with high scores for collaborating with colleagues ($M = 4.53$) and engaging the school community ($M = 4.64$). These results lend support to Guskey's (2002) assertion that ongoing engagement and professional collaboration are crucial for sustained instructional improvement. Furthermore, the high peer ratings show that the school environment fosters a culture of cooperation and shared professional responsibility.

In conclusion, the information shows that, despite their somewhat conservative self-rate, teachers are perceived by others as being highly engaged in professional and community activities. Their outreach to families and communities, along with their cooperation with colleagues, improves the learning environment and has a positive impact on student development. These results are consistent with the broader body of research on family-school partnerships and professional learning communities, which emphasizes that enhancing teaching performance requires cultivating relationships among the community, the home, and the school to promote comprehensive student success.

Table 23: Level of Teaching Performance in terms of Personal Growth and Professional Development

Indicators	Self/Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
As a teacher...									
1. I actively participate in school meetings, trainings, and discussions.	4.59	0.54	O	4.67	0.59	O	4.55	0.58	O
2. I pursue higher education or advanced studies to improve teaching competence.	4.32	0.72	VS	4.59	0.63	O	4.54	0.58	O
3. I stay updated with the latest trends and research in education.	4.26	0.69	VS	4.66	0.60	O	4.56	0.58	O
4. I develop a personal improvement plan based on self-reflection and ongoing learning.	4.38	0.66	VS	4.64	0.61	O	4.59	0.56	O
5. I demonstrate a commitment to lifelong learning by continuously improving teaching skills.	4.51	0.52	O	4.66	0.60	O	4.51	0.53	O
Overall	4.41	0.62	VS	4.64	0.61	O	4.58	0.57	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O); 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS); 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S); 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US); 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI)

Table 23 presents the level of teaching performance in the domain of Personal Growth and Professional Development, based on assessments by teachers, students, and peers. The overall mean indicates that teachers rate themselves as Very Satisfactory ($m = 4.41$, $SD = 0.62$), while both students ($m = 4.64$, $SD = 0.61$) and peers ($m = 4.58$, $SD = 0.57$) evaluate their performance as Outstanding. The difference reveals a prevalent pattern of educators reflecting critically on themselves, indicating humility or an awareness of their shortcomings.

In the teacher's self-assessment, the highest-rated indicator was "I actively participate in school meetings, trainings, and discussions" ($m = 4.59$), falling within the Outstanding range. The results of Desimore (2009) highlight that active engagement in professional learning communities greatly improves teaching effectiveness and student achievement. However, the teachers gave themselves lower ratings on indicators such as "I stay updated with the latest trends and research in education" ($m = 4.26$) and "I pursue higher education or advanced studies" ($m = 4.32$), which were marked as Very Satisfactory. This may reflect practical constraints, such as time, resources, or a lack of institutional support for continued formal education.

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Students provided Outstanding ratings across all indicators, particularly in “commitment to lifelong learning” (m=4.66) and “staying updated with latest educational trends” (m=4.66). These results suggest that students observe and appreciate their teachers’ efforts to enhance their competencies and improve classroom instruction. Avalos (2011), asserts that students view learning environments as more dynamic and effective when teachers participate in continuous professional development and incorporate it into their instruction.

Peers also evaluated the teachers’ performance as Outstanding, especially on “demonstrating commitment to lifelong learning” (m=4.61) and “developing personal improvements plans” (m=4.59). The school environment's culture of professionalism and ongoing development is highlighted by this peer recognition. According to Guskey (2002), enhanced teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes are closely associated with collegial collaboration and professional development.

According to the data, teachers are seen by their peers and students as being very dedicated to their own development, even though they may feel constrained in their efforts to further their education or stay up to date with current trends. Because high-quality teaching is based on collaborative efforts, reflective practice, and ongoing professional development, these perceptions are crucial. According to the findings, creating environments that encourage professional growth not only increases teacher effectiveness but also has a favorable impact on student achievement.

Table 24: Summary Table on Level of Teaching Performance

Indicators	Self/ Teacher			Students			Peer		
	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI	Mean	SD	VI
Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	4.55	0.56	O	4.64	0.60	O	4.57	0.58	O
Learning Environment	4.54	0.58	O	4.64	0.62	O	4.56	0.60	O
Diversity of Learners	4.57	0.55	O	4.55	0.72	O	4.54	0.64	O
Curriculum and Planning	4.57	0.57	O	4.59	0.65	O	4.57	0.60	O
Assessment and Reporting	4.54	0.56	O	4.60	0.66	O	4.58	0.59	O
Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	4.44	0.63	VS	4.63	0.62	O	4.59	0.58	O
Personal Growth and Professional Development	4.41	0.62	VS	4.64	0.61	O	4.58	0.57	O
Overall	4.52	0.58	O	4.61	0.64	O	4.57	0.59	O

Legend: 4.50-5.00 Outstanding (O), 3.50-4.49 Very Satisfactory (VS), 2.50-3.49 Satisfactory (S), 1.50-2.49 Unsatisfactory (US), 1.00-1.49 Needs Improvement (NI).

Table 24 presents the overall level of teaching performance across seven key domains, as rated by teachers (self-assessment, students, and peers). Across all source of evaluation, the mean score falls within the “Outstanding” (4.50-5.00) range, except for two indicators under the self-assessment category: “Community Linkages and Professional Engagement” (m=4.44), and Personal Growth and Professional Development” (m=4.41), which are rated “Very Satisfactory.” The overall composite means are: 4.52 (teachers), 4.61 (students), and 4.57 (peers), indicating the teachers are generally perceived as highly effective in their classroom performance and professional conduct.

Among the domains, the highest ratings from all three groups are consistently observed in “Content Knowledge and Pedagogy” (self: 4.55; students 4.64; peer: 4.56), affirming the critical role of subject mastery and a supportive classroom climate in instructional quality. According to Shulman (1987), educators who possess in-depth subject-matter expertise are able to create and present lessons that encourage comprehension and critical thinking in their students. A well-run and courteous classroom environment also has a significant impact on student achievement, as noted by Marzano (2003).

The area of “Diversity of Learners” also garnered strong “Outstanding” ratings from all groups (self: 4.57; students: 4.55; peer: 4.54), indicating that teachers are effectively addressing the varied learning needs of students. This supports the findings of Tomlinson's (2001) research on differentiated instruction, which contends that a key component of good teaching is being sensitive to the diversity of students.

Although still within the Outstanding range, the relatively lower mean in “Curriculum and Planning” (m = 4.57 across three sources) suggests room for improvement in integrating innovative and contextually relevant strategies. According to studies like Drake & Reid (2010), curriculum alignment with students' realities is crucial for maximizing the impact of learning.

The domain “Assessment and Reporting” (self: 4.54; students: 4.60; peer: 4.58) was also rated highly, consistent with the findings of Black and William (1998) who argue that formative assessment practices, particularly when paired with timely feedback, enhance learning outcomes.

However, the two domains that slightly trailed in teacher self-assessment were “Community Linkages and Professional Engagement” and “Personal Growth and Professional Development,” both rated Very Satisfactory by teachers themselves (m=4.44 and 4.41, respectively), while students and peers gave Outstanding ratings. This disparity may indicate a tendency for teachers to self-reflect more critically on their engagement with external stakeholders and their own professional growth.

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According to Guskey (2002) and Avalos (2011), community service and ongoing professional development are crucial elements of long-term teaching excellence.

In sum, the data reflect a strong and consistent teaching performance across core competencies, with the highest strengths in pedagogical expertise, inclusive learning environments, and assessment practices. The slightly lower self-perceptions in external engagement and professional development suggest areas where support systems or institutional encouragement could further elevate teaching standards.

Table 25: Test of Significant Relationship between Types of Leisure Engagement and Sustainable Well-being

Types of Leisure Engagement	Sustainable Well-Being				
	Emotional	Physical	Social	Workplace	Societal
Active	0.448**	0.571**	0.389**	0.379**	0.459**
Passive	0.448**	0.442**	0.402**	0.380**	0.333**
Social	0.555**	0.584**	0.517**	0.463**	0.555**
Cognitive	0.366**	0.462**	0.340**	0.379**	0.356**
Creative	0.339**	0.489**	0.351**	0.349**	0.417**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 25 presents the correlation coefficients between different types of leisure engagement (active, passive, social, cognitive, and creative) and various dimensions of sustainable well-being (emotional, physical, social, workplace, and societal). All correlation values are statistically significant at either the 0.05 or 0.01 levels, indicating meaningful relationships between leisure activities and the well-being dimensions. The strength of the correlations ranges from moderate to strong, suggesting that increased participation in various leisure types is positively associated with enhanced sustainable well-being among teachers.

Active leisure exhibits a strong and significant relationship with physical well-being ($r = 0.571$, $p < 0.01$) and societal well-being ($r = 0.459$, $p < 0.01$). These results suggest that physical activity, including sports, exercise, and outdoor pursuits, enhances physical well-being and promotes a stronger sense of community. This supports the findings of Iwasaki (2007) and Kuykendall, Tay, and Ng's (2015) Leisure Studies, which highlight the positive effects of physical leisure on stress reduction and physical health. The positive relationships with emotional well-being ($r = 0.448$) and social well-being ($r = 0.389$) support the role of active engagement in enhancing mood and interpersonal connections.

Passive leisure activities (e.g., watching TV, listening to music) are positively correlated with all well-being domains, with a particularly strong association observed with emotional well-being ($r = 0.448$) and physical well-being ($r = 0.442$). Pressman et al. (2009) found that relaxation-based leisure significantly contributes to positive emotions and physical health, supporting the idea that passive leisure, despite being generally regarded as less stimulating, still offers restorative benefits and aids in stress recovery, particularly emotionally.

Social leisure activities such as gatherings, conversations, and group hobbies show the strongest correlations across all domains. Notably, social leisure has the highest correlations with physical well-being ($r = 0.584$), emotional well-being ($r = 0.555$), and societal well-being ($r = 0.555$). This demonstrates the importance of social interactions in community involvement and overall life satisfaction. Social support from social leisure is one of the most reliable indicators of resilience and well-being, particularly for educators who frequently suffer from emotional exhaustion (Cohen & Wills, 1985; Myers, 2000).

Cognitive leisure activities, such as reading, puzzles, or intellectual discussions, exhibit significant yet moderate relationships, particularly with physical well-being ($r = 0.462$) and workplace well-being ($r = 0.379$). To enhance professional decision-making and job satisfaction, these activities promote reflective thinking and mental stimulation. Cognitive leisure enhances life satisfaction and reduces burnout by providing mental enrichment, according to research by Newman et al. (2014).

Creative activities, such as arts, crafts, and writing, are positively related to all well-being domains, particularly physical ($r = 0.489$) and societal ($r = 0.417$) well-being. These results highlight the integrative benefit of creative engagement in enhancing personal expression and community participation. According to research by Reis et al. (2000) and Forgeard and Mecklenburg (2013), engaging in creative pursuits helps individuals develop positive affect, self-esteem, and intrinsic motivation—all of which are essential for long-term well-being.

According to the data, there is a statistically significant correlation between various aspects of sustainable well-being and all types of leisure activities. The most significant of these is social leisure, which has the strongest correlation with all measures of well-being, particularly social, emotional, and physical. This highlights the importance of supporting teachers' social connections to promote their overall well-being. Additionally, creative and active leisure activities are essential for promoting physical well-being and greater community involvement. The results highlight how promoting teachers varied and balanced leisure activities

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can significantly improve their long-term personal and professional well-being, which in turn affects their effectiveness and performance as educators.

Table 26: Test of Significant Relationship between Degree of Leisure Engagement and Sustainable Well-being

Degree of Leisure of Engagement	Sustainable Well-Being				
	Emotional	Physical	Social	Workplace	Societal
Frequency	0.544**	0.600**	0.532**	0.499**	0.487**
Intensity	0.444**	0.569**	0.452**	0.436**	0.503**
Quality	0.544**	0.554**	0.603**	0.529**	0.488**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

**. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 26 presents the correlation coefficients between the degree of leisure engagement, measured in frequency, intensity, and quality, and various dimensions of sustainable well-being, including emotional, physical, social, workplace, and societal well-being. All correlations are statistically significant at the 0.01 level, indicating strong and meaningful relationships between how teachers engage in leisure and their overall well-being.

The frequency with which teachers engage in leisure activities demonstrates a strong positive correlation with all dimensions of well-being, most notably with physical well-being ($r = 0.600$), followed by emotional well-being ($r = 0.544$) and social well-being ($r = 0.532$). This suggests that engaging in leisure activities on a regular basis improves social connection, emotional stability, and physical health. These results align with Iwasaki's (2007) assertion that regular leisure time serves as a stress reliever and promotes overall health. Similar findings were reported by Kuykendall, Tay, and Ng (2015), who discovered that regular leisure activities promote social relationships, physical renewal, and emotional healing.

The intensity or level of psychological and physical investment during leisure activities also shows significant correlation with all well-being indicators, with the strongest link to physical well-being ($r=0.569$) and societal well-being ($r=0.503$). This implies that teachers' physical health and sense of community belonging are more significantly impacted when they fully engage in leisure activities like intense exercise, the performing arts, or service-oriented engagement. Strong leisure participation fosters self-determination and long-term well-being by offering greater fulfillment and meaning, claims Caldwell (2005). Additionally, these intense experiences promote what Csikszentmihalyi (1990) calls "flow," which is essential for mental clarity and renewal, particularly in high-stress occupations like teaching.

Among the three degrees, the quality of leisure engagement stands out for having the highest correlation with social well-being ($r = 0.603$) and a strong correlation with emotional well-being ($r = 0.544$) and workplace well-being ($r = 0.529$). This suggests that teachers' social connections and job satisfaction are greatly influenced by meaningful and fulfilling leisure activities rather than just frequent or intense ones. Activities that align with one's values, reflect one's interests, or offer opportunities for creativity and self-expression are examples of high-quality leisure. Newman et al. (2014) provide support for this, emphasizing that leisure quality predicts well-being more strongly than frequency alone. Furthermore, people who enjoy their leisure more report better psychological and physical health outcomes, according to Pressman et al. (2009).

According to the data, teachers' long-term well-being is strongly correlated with their level of leisure participation, particularly in terms of frequency and quality. Notably, social and workplace well-being are most strongly correlated with leisure quality, underscoring the importance of engaging in fulfilling leisure activities in enhancing interpersonal relationships and professional effectiveness. Based on these findings, schools and educational institutions should encourage teachers to engage in frequent, intense, and high-quality leisure activities, in addition to promoting a work-life balance. Promoting such involvement may result in improved classroom performance, stronger social networks, healthier lifestyles, and increased emotional resilience, all of which would eventually help teachers and their students.

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Table 27: Test of the Significant Relationship between Types of Leisure Engagement and Teaching Performance

Types of Leisure Engagement	Teaching Performance						
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Learning Environment	Diversity of Learners	Curriculum and Planning	Assessment and Reporting	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Personal Growth and Professional Development
Active	0.236**	0.251**	0.246**	0.293**	0.214*	0.286**	0.408**
Passive	0.473**	0.431**	0.462**	0.422**	0.432**	0.386**	0.445**
Social	0.345**	0.392**	0.376**	0.405**	0.354**	0.405**	0.481**
Cognitive	0.343**	0.351**	0.390**	0.362**	0.380**	0.347**	0.424**
Creative	0.291**	0.283**	0.220**	0.200*	0.220**	0.297**	0.338**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 27 presents the Pearson correlation coefficients indicating relationships between different types of leisure engagement – active, passive, social, cognitive and creative – and the seven indicators of teaching performance, namely: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. All relationships reported are statistically significant, either at the *0.05 level (marked) or the more stringent **0.01 level (marked), indicating reliable associations between teachers’ leisure activities and their teaching effectiveness.

Active leisure, such as physical exercise or sports, shows a moderate but significant positive correlation with all teaching performance indicators, highest with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.408^{**}$) and Curriculum and Planning ($r = 0.293^{**}$). This suggests that physically active teachers may demonstrate higher professional initiative and better planning competencies. These findings support the claims made by Ratey (2008) that physical activity improves motivation, concentration, and brain function—all of which are essential components of good instruction. According to Rasberry et al. (2011), teachers' physical health is associated with lower levels of burnout and better performance in educational settings.

Passive leisure activities, such as reading, watching educational programs, or listening to music, exhibit the strongest overall correlation across all teaching indicators, particularly with Content Knowledge and Pedagogy ($r = 0.473^{**}$) and Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.455^{**}$). These results suggest that, although passive leisure may appear less active, it is crucial for teachers' professional development and cognitive enrichment. Passive leisure activities can support knowledge acquisition and mental recovery, allowing teachers to return to the classroom with greater concentration and knowledge (Kuykendall, Tay, & Ng, 2015).

Social leisure, including participation in community events or bonding with friends, is significantly associated with all dimensions of teaching, especially Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.481^{**}$) and Curriculum and Planning ($r = 0.405^{**}$). These connections lend credence to the notion that social interactions offer chances for group learning, the exchange of teaching methods, and emotional support. Furthermore, Spilt, Koomen, and Thijs (2011) stress that classroom management and teacher morale are enhanced by robust interpersonal networks.

Cognitive leisure – activities that stimulate intellectual engagement, such as puzzle-solving, reading scholarly works, or attending lectures – is strongly correlated with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.424^{**}$) and Assessment and Reporting ($r = 0.380^{**}$). These findings highlight how intellectually stimulating activities refine teachers’ analytical and reflective capabilities.

Creative leisure, such as drawing, writing, or crafting, also shows statistically significant relationship across all teaching dimensions, most notably with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.388^{**}$) and Community Linkages ($r = 0.297^{**}$). These imply that teachers' flexibility and capacity to engage with the community are improved when they participate in artistic or expressive endeavors. According to Richards (2010), being creative in leisure time improves problem-solving skills and encourages the development of innovative teaching methods. In addition to being more adept at creating differentiated instruction, creative teachers are frequently more approachable and willing to collaborate with the community.

In summary, the data affirms that various forms of leisure engagement significantly enhance teaching performance, with passive, social, and cognitive leisure showing the most robust correlations across teaching indicators. Notably, Personal Growth and Professional Development consistently demonstrated strong correlation with all types of leisure, underlining the idea that teachers who invest in meaningful leisure also tend to grow professionally. These results underscore the importance of promoting a healthy work-life balance among educators, not merely for personal wellness but as a mechanism to sustain and elevate teaching quality and classroom performance. Schools and policymakers should encourage diverse forms of leisure as part of teacher well-being programs to maximize both personal and institutional outcomes.

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Table 28: Test of the Significant Relationship between Degree of Leisure Engagement and Teaching Performance

Degree of Leisure Engagement	Teaching Performance						
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Learning Environment	Diversity of Learners	Curriculum and Planning	Assessment and Reporting	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Personal Growth and Professional Development
Frequency	0.404**	0.436**	0.387**	0.405**	0.390**	0.417**	0.494**
Intensity	0.344**	0.345**	0.321**	0.314**	0.356**	0.370**	0.460**
Quality	0.439**	0.470**	0.473**	0.487**	0.480**	0.443**	0.454**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 28 presents the correlation coefficients between the degree of leisure engagement (measured by frequency, intensity, and quality) and the seven dimensions of teaching performance: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, and Personal Growth and Professional Development. All correlations are statistically significant at either the 0.05 or 0.01 levels, indicating consistent and meaningful associations.

The frequency of leisure engagement shows moderate, statistically significant positive correlations with all teaching performance indicators, most notably with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.494^{**}$) and Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.417^{**}$). This suggests that teachers who frequently engage in leisure activities are more likely to exhibit enhanced professional development and stronger community involvement. These results are consistent with those of Kuykendall, Tay, and Ng (2015), who observed that regular leisure activities enhance motivation, self-efficacy, and mental restoration—all of which promote professional development and improved teaching results.

Intensity, or the level of energy or emotional investment in leisure, also correlates positively with teaching performance, though with slightly lower coefficients compared to frequency and quality. The strongest link appears with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.460^{**}$) and Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.370^{**}$). This suggests that educators who engage in leisure activities on a deep level may develop greater resilience, creativity, and reflective and collaborative practices. Iwasaki (2007) asserts that leisure's psychological impact aids in personal growth and can assist teachers in managing the demands of their jobs and workplace stress.

Among the three degrees, quality of leisure engagement shows the strongest correlations across nearly all teaching performance indicators, particularly with Curriculum and Planning ($r = 0.487^{**}$), Diversity of Learners ($r = 0.473$), and Assessment and Reporting ($r = 0.480^{**}$). These findings highlight the fact that teachers' professional capacities are most positively impacted by the significance, relevance, and fulfillment they derive from their leisure activities, rather than the frequency or intensity of these activities. High-quality leisure offers intrinsic fulfillment, which enhances creativity, adaptability, and decision-making skills—essential for instructional planning, assessment, and responsiveness to student diversity—as noted by Newman, Tay, and Diener (2014).

The findings indicate that all degrees of leisure engagement, when frequent, intense, and of high quality, significantly contribute to improved teaching performance. Notably, Personal Growth and Professional Development consistently demonstrate the strongest relationship across all leisure engagement types, affirming that meaningful leisure is crucial in fostering teachers' continuous improvement. Moreover, the quality of leisure engagement appears to be the most influential factor, suggesting that experiences perceived as enriching and satisfying are conducive to enriching classroom performance.

This is consistent with the Sustainable Well-Being theory (Dodge et al., 2012), which posits that achieving well-being requires striking a balance between resources and challenges, as well as engaging in meaningful activities. Good leisure is an essential resource for teachers, supporting their emotional and cognitive reserves and ultimately improving their professional practice.

In conclusion, teachers who frequently, deeply, and meaningfully engage in leisure activities tend to be more effective in delivering content, managing diverse classrooms, planning curriculum, assessing student progress, and engaging with the broader community. These findings reinforce the need for schools and the education system to recognize leisure not as a luxury but as a strategic investment in teacher well-being and professional excellence. Programs and policies that promote balanced lifestyles and encourage high-quality leisure could play a significant role in elevating teaching standards and sustaining educators in the long term.

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Table 29: Test of the Significant Relationship between Sustainable Well-Being and Teaching Performance

Sustainable Well-Being	Teaching Performance						
	Content Knowledge and Pedagogy	Learning Environment	Diversity of Learners	Curriculum and Planning	Assessment and Reporting	Community Linkages and Professional Engagement	Personal Growth and Professional Development
Emotional	0.505**	0.491**	0.472**	0.483**	0.462**	0.575**	0.601**
Physical	0.415**	0.414**	0.352**	0.397**	0.343**	0.446**	0.590**
Social	0.576**	0.571**	0.511**	0.518**	0.466**	0.619**	0.596**
Workplace	0.482**	0.436**	0.383**	0.397**	0.348**	0.505**	0.579**
Societal	0.445**	0.503**	0.401**	0.398**	0.372**	0.533**	0.576**

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).
 **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 29 demonstrates a set of positive and statistically significant correlations ($p < 0.01$) between five dimensions of Sustainable Well-Being (Emotional, Physical, Social, Workplace, and Societal) and seven core indicators of Teaching Performance: Content Knowledge and Pedagogy, Learning Environment, Diversity of Learners, Curriculum and Planning, Assessment and Reporting, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement, Personal Growth and Professional Development. These results underscore the critical role that various aspects of well-being play in shaping and enhancing teacher effectiveness.

Emotional well-being displayed consistently strong correlations with all teaching performance indicators, most notably with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.601^{**}$) and Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.575^{**}$). These findings suggest that emotionally healthy teachers – those who experience frequent positive emotions and effective emotional regulation – are more capable of self-improvement, collaboration, and community involvement. This supports the findings of Jennings and Greenberg (2009), who discovered that educators who are emotionally healthy exhibit higher levels of patience, resilience, and reflective ability—all of which improve instructional strategies.

Physical well-being also correlated significantly with all indicators, with the highest correlations being observed for Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.590^{**}$) and Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.466^{**}$). Though slightly lower than emotional and social well-being, the results highlight that physically healthy teachers are more energized and engaged in both personal and professional development activities. Viac and Fraser's (2020) research confirms that teachers who are in good physical health have higher instructional stamina, lower absenteeism, and improved classroom engagement.

Social well-being yielded some of the strongest correlations in the table, particularly with Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.619^{**}$) and Content Knowledge and Pedagogy ($r = 0.576^{**}$). These findings suggest that teachers who experience social support and connection interact more successfully with students and professional communities. According to Zins et al. (2004), strong social networks encourage teamwork, information exchange, and emotional support—all of which are essential for successful teaching and long-term job satisfaction.

Workplace well-being also demonstrated significant positive relationships, most strongly with Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.579^{**}$) and Community Linkages ($r = 0.505^{**}$). Teachers are more likely to participate in professional development opportunities and larger educational initiatives when they feel safe, appreciated, and supported in their educational settings. Collie, Shapka, and Perry (2012) found that a favorable school climate increases teacher motivation, commitment, and performance, lending credence to this finding.

Societal well-being showed notable associations with Community Linkages and Professional Engagement ($r = 0.533^{**}$) and Personal Growth and Professional Development ($r = 0.576^{**}$), indicating that teachers who feel respected and valued by society are more driven to improve themselves and contribute actively to the educational community. Day and Gu (2010) assert that the desire to succeed in one's role, job satisfaction, and teacher identity are all strengthened by society's acceptance of the teaching profession.

Across all domains of sustainable well-being, the strongest and most consistent correlations were observed with Personal Growth and Professional Development, suggesting that well-being, particularly emotional, social, and societal, serves as a foundation for teachers' ongoing learning and improvement. Furthermore, Community Linkages and Professional Engagement repeatedly emerged as a closely linked domain, emphasizing that well-being supports teachers in forming and sustaining external relationships critical to student development and school success. Together, these results support the PERMA model of well-being (Seligman, 2011), which emphasizes the importance of relationships, emotional health, and purpose in achieving optimal functioning both personally and professionally, particularly in human-centered domains such as education.

The results clearly demonstrate that sustainable well-being is positively and significantly related to teaching performance, with robust associations found in areas related to teacher development and professional engagement. This underscores the importance

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of supporting teachers' holistic well-being as a strategic imperative for educational quality. Schools. Therefore, invest in programs that promote emotional, physical, social, and workplace wellness, cultivating a thriving, effective, and sustainable teaching workforce.

Table 30: Test of the Mediating Effect of Sustainable Well-Being on the Type of Leisure Activities and Teaching Performance

Mediation Analysis	Estimate	SE	95% CI		Z	P
			Lower	Upper		
Effect						
Indirect	0.202	0.040	0.124	0.280	5.090	<.001
Direct	0.109	0.054	0.002	0.215	2.000	0.046
Total	0.311	0.049	0.214	0.407	6.290	<.001
Path Estimates						
Type of Leisure Activities→ Sustainable Well-Being	0.516	0.059	0.401	0.632	8.750	<.001
Sustainable Well-Being→ Teaching Performance	0.391	0.063	0.269	0.514	6.250	<.001
Type of Leisure Activities→ Teaching Performance	0.109	0.054	0.002	0.215	2.000	0.046

The direct effect of the type of leisure activities on teaching performance is 0.109 (SE = 0.054, 95% CI: 0.002 to 0.215, Z = 2.000, p = 0.046), which remains statistically significant, albeit weaker than the indirect effect. This indicates that types of leisure activities influence teaching performance both directly and indirectly, with the more decisive influence occurring through the enhancement of well-being. This direct link suggests that even without considering well-being, diverse leisure activities (e.g., active, social, creative engagement) provide intrinsic benefits such as cognitive stimulation, emotional regulation, and social bonding, which can enhance pedagogical effectiveness. This aligns with Iwasaki's (2007) observation that leisure can support both personal functioning and well-being.

The total effect (combining both direct and indirect effects) is 0.311 (SE = 0.049, 95% CI: 0.214 TO 0.407, Z = 6.290, p <.001), which is statistically significant. This overall finding confirms that leisure activities have a meaningful and positive impact on teaching performance, and that a significant portion of this relationship is mediated through sustainable well-being.

The path coefficient from type of leisure activities to sustainable well-being is substantial and significant ($\beta = 0.516$, p < .001), showing that teachers who regularly engage in a variety of leisure activities – whether active, social, or creative – report significantly higher levels of emotional, physical, social, workplace, and societal well-being. This finding is consistent with research by Newman et al. (2014), which demonstrated that leisure activities promote relatedness, autonomy, and mastery, all of which contribute to improved psychological and social well-being.

The subsequent path from sustainable well-being to teaching performance is also significant ($\beta = 0.391$, p < .001), confirming that teachers with higher well-being tend to perform better in the classroom across various domains, including instructional planning, learning environment, assessment, and professional growth. This aligns with the conclusion of Roffey (2012), who found that well-being has a positive influence on teacher attitudes, classroom climate, and student relationships.

The findings from Table 30 demonstrate a significant mediating role of sustainable well-being in the relationship between types of leisure activities and teaching performance. This suggests that while leisure activities directly support teacher effectiveness, their greater contribution lies in enhancing teachers' overall well-being, both emotionally and professionally. Promoting holistic wellness through meaningful leisure engagement should be viewed as a strategic approach to enhancing teaching quality, underscoring the importance of school systems supporting work-life balance and well-being programs for educators.

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Table 31: Test of the Mediating Effect of Sustainable Well-Being on Degree of Leisure Engagement and Teaching Performance

Mediation Analysis	Estimate	SE	95% CI		Z	P
			Lower	Upper		
Effect						
Indirect	0.222	0.047	0.130	0.315	4.710	<.001
Direct	0.167	0.064	0.042	0.293	2.630	0.009
Total	0.390	0.052	0.287	0.493	7.450	<.001
Path Estimates						
Degree of Leisure Engagement → Sustainable Well-Being	0.635	0.061	0.516	0.754	10.440	<.001
Sustainable Well-Being → Teaching Performance	0.350	0.066	0.220	0.480	5.270	<.001
Degree of Leisure Engagement → Teaching Performance	0.167	0.064	0.042	0.293	2.630	0.009

Table 31 presents the result of a mediation analysis aimed at understanding whether sustainable well-being significantly mediates the relationship between the degree of leisure engagement (measured by frequency, intensity, and quality) and teaching performance. The results reveal both direct and indirect effects as statistically significant, with sustainable well-being serving as a partial mediator in this relationship.

The indirect effect is 0.222 (SE = 0.047, 95% CI: 0.130–0.315, Z = 4.710, p < .001), indicating that a significant portion of the influence of leisure engagement on teaching performance occurs through the enhancement of sustainable well-being. The confidence interval excludes zero, affirming the robustness of these findings. This suggests that teachers who frequently and meaningfully engage in leisure activities (of high quality and intensity) experience improved emotional, physical, social, and workplace well-being, which, in turn, enhances their teaching effectiveness. This aligns with Keyes (2007), who argued that flourishing mental health—characterized by emotional and social well-being—strongly predicts occupational performance and civic engagement.

The direct effect of the degree of leisure engagement on teaching performance is 0.167 (SE = 0.064, 95% CI: 0.042–0.293, Z = 2.630, p = 0.009), which remains statistically significant even when accounting for well-being. This indicates that leisure engagement has a dual pathway to influence teaching effectiveness: both directly supports professional functioning and indirectly boosts performance through improved well-being. This finding supports the work of Iwasaki and Mannell (2000), who highlighted how high-quality leisure serves as a coping resource that directly affects psychological resilience and job performance.

The total effect – the combined impact of direct and indirect pathways – is 0.390 SE = 0.052, 95% CI: 0.287–0.493, Z = 7.450, p < .001, signifying a strong and statistically significant relationship between the degree of leisure engagement and teaching performance. This suggests that fostering high levels of leisure engagement among teachers contributes significantly to their instructional quality, planning, learner engagement, and professional development.

The path coefficient from degree of leisure engagement to sustainable well-being is 0.635 (SE = 0.061, p < .001), indicating a strong and positive relationship. Teachers who frequently engage in high-quality and intense leisure activities tend to report significantly better well-being across all dimensions, including emotional, physical, social, workplace, and societal aspects. This supports the findings of Haworth and Lewis (2005), who emphasized that fulfilling leisure experiences build a reservoir of positive affect, satisfaction, and vitality – all of which enhance work-life integration. In comparison, the path from sustainable well-being to teaching performance is 0.350 (SE = 0.066, p < .001), reinforcing the importance of holistic well-being in professional practice. When teachers are well-physically, emotionally, and socially, they are more capable of fostering positive learning environments, delivering effective instruction, and engaging in meaningful professional development. This finding is consistent with Day and Gu (2009), who stressed that well-being is a cornerstone of sustained teacher effectiveness, particularly in high-stress educational environments.

Table 31 provides compelling evidence that sustainable well-being significantly mediates the relationship between the degree of leisure engagement and teaching performance. Teachers who frequently and meaningfully engage in leisure activities report better well-being, which in turn enhances their classroom performance across key indicators such as curriculum planning, assessment, and personal growth. Notably, the direct effect also remains significant, highlighting that leisure engagement itself, beyond its impact on well-being, plays a pivotal role in shaping professional outcomes. This underscores the importance of institutional support for work-life balance and recreational opportunities as a strategic investment in teacher effectiveness.

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CONCLUSIONS

The findings provide empirical support for the idea that teachers who actively engage in meaningful leisure activities tend to experience higher levels of sustainable well-being, which in turn enhances their teaching performance.

The correlation analyses further revealed that all types and degrees of leisure engagement were significantly associated with both sustainable well-being and teaching performance. Moreover, sustainable well-being was significantly related to teaching performance across all domains, emphasizing its central role in educational effectiveness.

Finally, the mediation analysis confirmed that sustainable well-being significantly mediates the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance. This finding illustrates that leisure engagement not only directly enhances teaching performance but also does so indirectly by fostering a sustained and holistic sense of well-being. The mediating effect of sustainable well-being reveals that teachers' performance is significantly influenced not only by their work environment but also by how they maintain personal balance and resilience through leisure and self-care practices.

Based on the findings of the study, the following conclusion is drawn:

1. There is a significant relationship on both types and degrees of leisure engagement between all dimensions of sustainable well-being.
2. There is a significant relationship between various types and degrees of leisure engagement and all domains of teaching performance.
3. There is a significant relationship between all dimensions of sustainable well-being and all domains of teaching performance. It is concluded that sustainable well-being makes a significant contribution to enhanced teaching performance.
4. Sustainable well-being was found to serve as a significant mediating variable between leisure engagement and teaching performance. The significant correlations between leisure engagement and well-being, as well as between well-being and teaching performance, support the presence of a mediating effect.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study. The following recommendations are proposed to enhance teaching performance by supporting leisure engagement and sustainable well-being among teachers:

1. Educational institutions may implement structured programs that support active, social, cognitive, and creative leisure activities for teachers. Since leisure engagement has been proven to contribute to both well-being and teaching performance significantly, this can be achieved through wellness programs, mindfulness sessions, recreational activities, and access to mental health support services. These programs can help teachers manage stress and recharge, thereby improving their overall teaching effectiveness.
2. Policymakers and school administrators may review current policies to ensure they respect the work-life balance of teachers. Teachers can maintain a better work-life balance by limiting after-school activities, controlling non-instructional workload, and establishing clear time-off policies.
3. Teachers may be encouraged to engage in personally fulfilling leisure activities, whether they be creative, social, physical, or cognitive, as these have been demonstrated to improve emotional health and job satisfaction.
4. Institutions ought to identify and incorporate indicators of well-being into their systems for evaluating teachers' performance. Shifting the culture away from performance pressure and toward holistic development is made easier by acknowledging the importance of personal well-being in achieving professional success.
5. Regular professional development programs ought to include instruction in time management, emotional resilience, and stress response. With these abilities, educators will be better equipped to manage the responsibilities of their jobs while maintaining their well-being.
6. School administrators may foster an environment where teachers feel appreciated and understood by fostering empathy, teamwork, and mutual support. Strong interpersonal ties at work have a significant impact on long-term well-being and, in turn, on teaching effectiveness.
7. Future researchers are encouraged to expand the scope of this study by exploring additional variables and using diverse research contexts. While this study focused on the mediating role of sustainable well-being in the relationship between leisure engagement and teaching performance, subsequent studies may consider investigating other potential mediators or moderators such as occupational stress, resilience, job satisfaction, or institutional support.

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